

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Evolution and Adaptation of Enzymes' Active Sites: Enzymes Use Functionally Similar Active Site for Same Type of Reactions with Structurally Similar Substrates Irrespective of the Organism

Peramachi Palanivelu *

Senior Professor and Head (Retd.), Department of Molecular Microbiology, School of Biotechnology, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai – 625 021, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 28(03), 1810-1835

Publication history: Received on 15 November 2025; revised on 21 December 2025; accepted on 24 December 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.28.3.4234>

Abstract

Enzymes have played a crucial role in the evolution of life on the planet Earth, as they could accelerate thermodynamically favourable reactions approximately a million times faster. The evolution of enzymes with their unique 3D structures and specific active sites for each reaction is still a mystery. Interestingly, now it is found that two different transferases from two different metabolic pathways use the same active site amino acids, suggesting that active sites of enzymes are designed based on the specific molecular interactions between the active site amino acids and their substrate molecules. The present data further reveal that not only the active site is designed for a particular biological reaction during evolution, but also adapted and conserved in all life forms, from viruses to humans. This is based on the fact that just two-point mutations, viz. S³⁵⁶ and Q³⁶³, instead of the conserved Phe³⁵⁶ and a positively charged residue K³⁶³, respectively, rendered the enzyme, fructosyl transferase from *Geobacillus stearothermophilus* inactive. The importance of these two amino acids in fructosyl transferases was further confirmed from analysis of hundreds of fructosyl transferase sequences from levan- and inulosucrases, and other glycoside hydrolase GH68 family of enzymes from a large number of organisms. The fructosyl transferases are bifunctional enzymes and function both as a hydrolase and as a transferase. The hydrolase uses a catalytic triad in its active site, viz. 2 Asp residues where one acts as the nucleophile and the other acts as the transition-state stabilizer and a Glu residue that acts as a general acid-base catalyst. Similarly, the transferase also uses a catalytic triad, viz. a positively charged amino acid residue, K/R/H, as the proton abstractor and an R at -3 from the proton abstractor as the donor selection amino acid and an Y or a branched chain amino acid with a G as the template-binding pair. It is interesting to note that the same catalytic triad is observed in the active sites of nucleotidyl transferases like DNA/RNA polymerases [1-3]. For example, the nucleotidyl transferase (*E. coli* DNA polymerase I) and the fructosyl transferase (*Bacillus subtilis* levansucrase) possess more or less the same active site structure, (-R⁴RS⁷⁵⁸AK⁷⁵⁸AINFLGIY⁷⁶⁶GM- and -D³⁵⁸SR³⁵⁸-GSK³⁶³MTIDGITSNDIYML³⁷⁷GY-, respectively) where K⁷⁵⁸ in the *E. coli* enzyme is shown to be the proton abstractor, the R at -4 as the nucleotide selection amino acid and the -YG- as the template-binding pair. Furthermore, extensive analysis of different DNA/RNA polymerases and fructosyl transferases from a large number organisms, from viruses to humans, revealed the same active site structure [1-3]. These data confirm that during evolution, not only similar active site is designed and used for the same types of reactions, but also conserved and adapted to all forms of life, from viruses to humans.

Keywords: Evolution of Life; Evolution of Enzyme Active Sites; Fructans; Fructosyl Transferases; Hydrolase Active Site; Fructosyl Transferase Active Site; Nucleotidyl Transferases; Nucleotidyl Transferase Active Site; Mechanisms of the Fructosyl and Nucleotidyl Transferases

* Corresponding author: Peramachi Palanivelu

1. Introduction

Understanding the origin of life is still a complex and a completely unsolved problem in biology. However, laboratory experiments suggest that life might have evolved in the early Earth by a series of progressive and spontaneous chemical reactions under the prevailing environmental conditions of the prebiotic era. The first phase of evolution, viz. the chemical evolution, actually set the very early stage for the development of life by the formation of simple organic molecules such as amino acids, simple sugars, fatty acids, nucleic acid bases, etc. from inorganic molecules. Such spontaneous formation of organic molecules from inorganic molecules is proved by groundbreaking experiments conducted by Urey [4] and Miller [5] in the 1950s where they simulated the conditions of early Earth's atmosphere and studied the formation of organic molecules. Miller and Urey [6] demonstrated that organic molecules such as amino acids could be spontaneously formed from inorganic compounds when an electrical arc (simulating lightning) was passed through a mixture of gases. Their seminal experiments suggested that electrical discharges might have played a significant role in the formation of organic compounds from a mixture of gases present in the primitive atmosphere.

Their findings of spontaneous formation of life's molecules in the primitive atmosphere were further confirmed by Criado-Reyes *et al.* [7]. They recently repeated the familiar Urey-Miller experiment, conducted about 70 years ago, but in a borosilicate vessel. Interestingly, they found a large number of additional compounds such as dipeptides, multi-carbon dicarboxylic acids, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon compounds (PAHs) and a complete panel of biological nucleobases in their reaction mixture. Furthermore, the natural formation of small peptides and oligonucleotides in the presence of inorganic catalysts like hydroxyapatite, clay, zeolites, etc. further advanced our knowledge on the evolution of life [8]. These experiments strongly support a widely accepted theory of "spontaneous generation," suggesting that chemical reactions could just start spontaneously when the reacting substances are kept in close proximity to each other. This theory of 'spontaneous formation' of life's molecules is further supported by a recent work by Mohajer *et al.* [9]. They have shown the spontaneous formation of urea, the simplest organic molecule and a key compound that connects chemistry and life and is also considered as a key molecule in the search for the origin of life. Its formation from ammonia and carbon dioxide requires either high pressures and temperatures, or, under milder conditions with catalysts or additional reagents. In contrast, Mohajer *et al.* [9] have demonstrated that the spontaneous formation of urea under ambient conditions (i.e., non-energetic conditions and without additional catalysts) from ammonia and carbon dioxide in the surface layer of aqueous droplets. Their experiment further corroborates that the evolutionary processes are spontaneous.

Further, additional advanced experiments on evolution have demonstrated that replicating autocatalytic RNA molecules could undergo spontaneous changes and that the variants of RNA molecules with the greatest autocatalytic activities prevailed in the prebiotic life [10]. Their results support the basis of the "RNA world" hypothesis. In support of this hypothesis, a recent study has shown that RNAs are not only autocatalytic, but also could help amino acids to assemble into peptides without a pre-existing protein machinery during evolution [10]. However, the "Metabolism First" camp argues that self-sustaining chemical networks should have evolved first for the self-replicating genetic molecules like RNA to use them. The 'Metabolism First' model suggests that life emerged as a result of simple chemical reactions, governed by the laws of chemistry and thermodynamics, rather than through improbable chance events.

The next crucial phase in the origin of life is the formation of 'protocells' that are enveloped with primitive type membrane structures, where the organic compounds that are formed are compartmentalized and the compartmentalized organic compounds with self-organization potential led to the formation of lower molecular weight compounds like simple oligopeptides, oligonucleotides, etc. Thus, they bridge chemistry and biology by establishing primitive metabolic activities inside them. The protocells later evolved into 'primitive cell' types. The primitive cells may be considered as the first living cells capable of basic metabolism and reproductive capabilities. Interestingly, small peptides, oligonucleotides that are assembled on inorganic matrixes like clay, silica, zeolites, etc., and other small molecules, nutrients, ions, etc. could also have diffused freely into the primitive cells expanding their metabolic capabilities [11]. It is also likely that at different prevailing environmental conditions on the planet Earth different types of protocells and primitive cells would have formed, giving rise to diversities. In the next phase, the glycan-based polymers would have formed a protective layer on the fragile cell membranes, leading to the formation of complete primitive cell types. The two crucial components of basic life processes, viz. enzymes (which are responsible for all the cellular reactions) and genetic materials (which carry the genetic information to the next generation) might have evolved much later.

Primitive types of catalytic activities in the primitive cells would have started with metal ions and minerals like clay, zeolites, etc. As each enzyme's active site is specific for its substrate, it would have formed after the binding of active site amino acids on to their respective existing substrates, followed by filling of the gaps between the active site amino acids with other amino acids and likely not *vice versa*. This is evidenced by the distance conservation between the active

site amino acids in enzymes. Then the enzymes could have formed their respective RNA molecules where three nucleobases (as a codon) recognize each of the amino acid and such codons are connected in the same order into a short RNA molecule representing that particular enzyme, which would later code for that enzyme. An intuitive addition of a Met codon at the start and a stop codon at the end make the translation events unidirectional. And, many such protein coding RNA molecules could have further assembled into a larger RNA molecule forming an RNA genome. The RNA genome, thus, carries all the molecular instructions of the enzymes in a cell. And, when the deoxyribonucleosides were available, the molecular instructions on the RNA molecule could have transferred to the more stable DNA molecule by complementary base-pairing. In the reverse direction, such DNA can give rise to RNA molecules (transcription) and the RNA molecules can give rise to enzymes (translation) which function in the cells as originally designed by nature. Therefore, it is tempting to speculate that the life's molecules could have evolved spontaneously, self-assembled and organized into primitive cell types, initiating all cellular reactions. The mutation and selection, addition(s) and deletion(s), are natural and progressive steps in the evolutionary process. As discussed elsewhere, enzymes have evolved over billions of years through natural selection, which act primarily at the level of biological function, and diverse types of enzymes are constantly evolved from mutation and selection, divergence of existing genes and recombination of domains. Further, adaptation to different new environments could also play a key role in further evolution of new enzymes with new biological functions. Besides, changes in the available chemicals, ions, minerals and environmental conditions could also favour further evolution of enzymes with new functions that are beneficial to the organisms.

In this communication, evidences are presented to show how two different unconnected enzymatic reactions, one in the carbohydrate metabolism and the other in the nucleic acid metabolism, use the same active site amino acids for polymerization reactions, which strongly supports the chemical basis of evolution enzymes and their active sites. Both the enzymes are classified under the Main class, 'Transferases', but one is a fructofuranosyl transferase and the other is a nucleotidyl transferase. The nucleotidyl transferases play the key role in DNA/RNA polymerases to polymerize the nucleobases into a DNA or an RNA. It is interesting to note that the requirement for such specialized nucleotidyl transferases to accurately replicate the genetic material is universal in all kingdoms of life and hence, they are also known as crucial 'life catalysts'. The properties, multiple sequence alignment (MSA) analysis and the mechanism of actions of DNA and RNA polymerases from viruses, plants to humans have been extensively analyzed and reported by the author [1-3]. Therefore, in this communication evidences are provided to support how these two different groups of enzymes use and have adapted the same active site amino acid structure to perform similar functions in all organisms.

1.1. Fructans and their Applications

Inulins, levans and fructooligosaccharides are collectively known as fructans. They mainly differ in their linkages and degree of polymerization (DP). The inulins and levans exhibit chain lengths of >20 DPs and the fructooligosaccharides are of only <20 DPs. Demand and interest for fructans have increased over the years, due to their versatile applications and with increased interest in healthy lifestyles as they exhibit many potential health benefits. In recent times, the global market for fructans has steadily increased, with an annual growth rate of >5%, and is expected to reach approximately 2.7 billion US dollars by 2026 [12]. The fructans are produced by a large number of organisms like bacteria, yeasts [13], higher fungi [14] and plants [15]. Bacterial levans (produced as exopolysaccharides, EPS) are much larger than those produced by plants and fungi with multiple branches and molecular weights ranging from 2 to 100 million Daltons [16]. Inulin-type fructans are mostly found in plants. The dicots accumulate them as long-term reserve carbohydrates, in underground storage organs such as roots and tubers and are mainly extracted from the plant sources like chicory, dahlia, yacon and Jerusalem artichoke as they accumulate up to 80% polysaccharides in their tubers [17-19]. In grasses, graminan (branched type fructans), levan, and neokestose-derived fructans mainly act as short-term storage compounds in stems, tiller bases, leaf sheaths, elongating leaf bases, and to a lesser extent in leaf blades and roots [17]. They find versatile applications in various industries and also in medicine. In industries, they are used as food thickeners, in cosmetics, as prebiotics, dietary fibres, mineral absorbing agents, anticancer agents, diabetic control agents, etc. Fructans exhibit many potential health benefits. As these fructans are non-digestible in our digestive system, they are considered as health-promoting 'prebiotics', i.e., they act as a food source for the beneficial gut bacteria. Therefore, they are gaining considerable attention the health industries as effective prebiotics to support the growth of beneficial gut bacteria, which play important roles in promoting digestive health, boosting the immune system, reducing the risk of chronic diseases, etc. [20-22]. Many bacteria, fungi and ~ 40,000 plant species use fructans as the primary carbohydrate reserves. Furthermore, it is found that in plants these fructans function as stabilizers of cell membranes and thus, confer tolerance to drought and frost. In plants, the fructan molecules are bound to the polar head groups of the lipid bilayer of the membrane to block water leakage during abiotic stress such as frost and drought [15, 23]. In addition to the above roles in industrial applications and as prebiotics, levan exhibits a wide range of specialized properties like film-forming ability, biodegradability, non-toxicity, self-aggregation, encapsulation, controlled release capacity, water retention, immunomodulatory activity, antimicrobial and anticancer activities, high biocompatibility

etc. With the strongest bio-adhesive properties and film-forming ability, levan could be used for healing wounds, burned tissues and for the development of bioresorbable electronic implants [24]. Furthermore, high DP fructans from bacteria are ideal substrates for the production of high fructose syrups (HFS), with very low glucose content. As levan is more soluble than inulin, it produces viscous solutions in water. In the industry, this property makes levan especially attractive as an emulsifier or encapsulating agent in a wide range of products, including biodegradable plastics, cosmetics, glues, textile coatings and detergents. These exceptional properties position levan as an attractive candidate for nature-based materials in food production, modern cosmetology, medicine, and pharmaceutical industries. Thus, with excellent medicinal properties and ease of production, microbial levans appear as a valuable and versatile biopolymer of the future.

1.2. Fructofuranosyl Transferases

The commonly used sugar, sucrose [α -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- β -D-fructofuranoside] is a non-reducing disaccharide, where its two monosaccharide units, viz. glucose and fructose are linked by a glycosidic bond. Unlike most of the other disaccharides, as both the reducing ends of the monosaccharide units are involved in the glycosidic bond formation, it becomes non-reducing. Furthermore, in sucrose, the glucose is in its pyranose form and the fructose is in its furanose form. It is metabolized mainly by at least four types of enzymes, i.e., i) invertases (EC 3.2.1.26), which hydrolyze the sucrose to produce 1 mole each of glucose and fructose, ii) inulosucrases (E.C 2.4.1.9), which hydrolyze the sucrose to produce inulin (with a molecular mass of about 10 Da) and glucose units, iii) levansucrases (E.C 2.4.1.10), which hydrolyze the sucrose to produce levan (with a molecular mass up to 1×10^6 Da) and glucose units and iv) dextransucrases (EC 2.4.1.5), which hydrolyze sucrose and produce dextran (with a molecular mass of about 1kDa to 2MDa) and fructose units. The chains of levan, inulin and dextran, like other biopolymers like starch, cellulose, and chitin grow stepwise by the repeated transfer of a hexosyl group (donor) to a growing acceptor molecule. These fructan-forming enzymes are commonly reported from bacteria, fungi and plants. Bacteria use the fructans and dextran as reserve EPS and utilize them by producing corresponding degradative enzymes like levanase, inulinase and dextransase when needed [25]. Among them, fructans are acid-labile, water-soluble, and polydisperse polymers of fructose built upon a sucrose starter unit. Between the two commonly occurring fructans, viz. inulin and levan, the inulosucrases polymerize fructosyl units into inulin which is mainly β -(2 \rightarrow 1) linked, whereas the levansucrases, form levan from fructosyl units which is mainly β -(2 \rightarrow 6) linked. Both belong to the Glycoside Hydrolase family GH68 (<http://afmb.cnrs-mrs.fr/CAZY>) and specifically belong to the hexosyltransferases [25]. Levansucrases, in general, display a five-bladed β -propeller architecture, where the catalytic residues which are responsible for sucrose hydrolysis are located in a negatively charged cavity [20, 26]. The microbial fructan synthesis is more efficient than the plant systems because it is synthesized from sucrose by a single enzyme reaction and exhibits homogeneous structures with occasional branches. In contrast, plant fructans are shorter and exhibit diverse structures, which result from a combination of catalytic actions of various enzymes, including sucrose:sucrose 1-fructosyltransferase (1-SST), fructan:fructan 1-fructosyltransferase (1-FFT), fructan:fructan 6G-fructosyltransferase (6G-FFT), and sucrose:fructan 6-fructosyltransferase (6-SFT). Fructosyltransferases (Fts) are also reported from fungi such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Aureobasidium*, *Kluyveromyces*, etc. Fungal Fts act on sucrose by cleaving the β -(2-1) linkage, releasing glucose, and then transferring the fructosyl units to an acceptor molecule. The fungal Ft from *Aspergillus* possesses both hydrolytic and transfructosylating activities as in other organisms. Interestingly, at sucrose concentrations >100 mM, the Fts exclusively exhibit a transfructosylation activity [27].

2. Materials and Methods

The protein sequence data of levansucrases, inulosucrases and other GH68 family of enzymes and DNA and RNA polymerases were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. Along with the conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis, and with the data already available from biochemical, site-directed mutagenesis (SDM) experiments and X-ray crystallographic analysis on these enzymes are used to confirm the possible amino acids at the active sites of these two different transferases, viz. fructofuranosyl and nucleotidyl transferases.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. MSA analysis of levansucrases and other GH68 family glycoside hydrolases fructosyl transferases

Figure 1 shows the MSA of levansucrases and GH68 family of fructosyl transferases from different bacteria, (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The sources of active and inactive fructosyl transferase enzymes are highlighted in yellow. The green arrow mark tentatively separates the hydrolytic and transferase domains. As the fructosyl transferases are bifunctional enzymes, they exhibit both hydrolase and transferase activities and each activity

is composed of a catalytic triad of three invariant or highly conserved amino acids. Furthermore, they also possess two highly conserved sucrose-binding sites. The N-terminal region is not conserved among them except for a few amino acids. However, an octapeptide -DVWDS/TWPL- is completely conserved in these enzymes where the second D is shown to be the catalytic nucleophile [18]. The second conserved peptide -EWSGSA- is found around 160 amino acids from the N-terminal. The first S is known to play an important role in binding to the Glc unit of sucrose. By SDM, the levansucrase of *Bacillus subtilis* SacB (-EWS¹⁶⁴), where the conserved S¹⁶⁴→A, showed that this is an important residue in maintaining the nucleophile position in the active site, suggesting that the motif is possibly involved in sucrose-binding [28]. The third highly conserved region in these enzymes is a large peptide -DNHTL/M/FRDPHYVED- located around 250 amino acids from the N-terminal. The -RDP- triad is conserved in all and is shown to bind the Fru unit of sucrose. The D in this triad is also shown to play a role in stabilizing the reaction intermediate during catalysis [18]. The acid-base catalytic E is found around 340 amino acids from the N-terminal and located in the highly conserved tetrapeptide -EIER- where the catalytic E is shown to act as the proton donor in catalysis [18]. The transferase module starts immediately after the hydrolytic module (indicated by a green arrow mark). The active site amino acids in the transferase module are highlighted in green. The catalytic site of transferases is also composed of a catalytic triad with an invariant basic amino acid K (proton abstractor), a template-binding pair -LG- (usually exists as a conserved triad -LGY/F) and an invariant amino acid R at -3, which is proposed in selecting incoming donor fructose units for polymerization. It is interesting to note that in the inactive levansucrase from *G. stearothermophilus*, the proton abstractor K is replaced by a Q (marked in red). Thus, this module is conserved in both fructosyl transferases and in nucleotidyl transferases. In the conserved pentapeptide -KWYLF- the invariant Y is also implicated in the interaction with the fructose donor and the F is replaced by an S in the inactive form of the levansucrase from *G. stearothermophilus* (marked in red).

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) MSA of levansucrases and other GH68 family glycoside hydrolase fructosyl transferases from bacteria

tr A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	DMINQH--GDDKFTVPSFDASTIKNIVESATKTDENGNKIKM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	108
tr A0AAX2EH38 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	EMIGQH--GDERYTVPSFDASSIKNIKSATKIDENGENEIKM	DVWDTWPL	QNP	113
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	EMIGQH--GDERYTVPSFDASSIKNIKSATKIDENGENEIKM	DVWDTWPL	QNP	113
tr A0A084GQG0 A0A084GQG0_METID	DMINQH--GDARYTVPKFDASKIENIPSAKKTTESGETMDI	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A612MEF7 A0A612MEF7_9BACI	DMINQH--GDARYTVPKFDESTIKNIIPSAKKVTESGETIDM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	DMI SQH--GDANFEVPKFDASSIKNIIPSAKKYDKDGNLIK	DVWDTWPL	QNA	110
tr A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	NMISQH--GDPRYTVPAFDESTIRNIPAAKTKTDENGNTIMM	DVWDTWPL	QNT	111
tr A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	DMIKQH--GDAKYTVPQFDASTIKNIIPAAQKVDENGNLMDI	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A926NJ10 A0A926NJ10_9BACI	EMALQH--GNEKFEVPKFDEKTIKNIPSAEG-----	LDVWDTWPL	QNA	101
tr A0A1G8F5H7 A0A1G8F5H7_9BACI	NMIDQH--GDPDFTVPSFDASTIENIPSAKKINEEGSEIDM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	DMINQH--GSDSFTVPEFDASTIENIPSAATKTGENEIVM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	DMINQH--GSDSFTVPEFDASTIDNIPSAATKTGENEIVM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A1R1RM81 A0A1R1RM81_9BACI	NIIKQH--DDPRFEVPPQFDASTIKNIIPSAKKYDENGKLM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	NMIRQH--GDPRYTVPEFDASTIVNIPSAQKYDENGKLM	DVWDTWPL	QTG	111
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	KIIGQH--GDSRYTVPFDESTIKNIIPSAKGYDEHGNVIDI	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A2N0Z5D7 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI	KMVQQ--SDPRYTVPTFDKTAIKNIIPSAKKTDENGNVIDI	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	KMTEQQ--NDSKFKVPAFDESTIKNIIPSAKGYDEKGNLID	DVWDTWPL	QNA	111
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	QIPGQLAEDKERFTVPAFDASKLKNIESATGFDDKGNKIL	DVWDTWPL	MNA	110
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	KLPQQH--DNARFEVPKFDADSRNIPTAQGYDKNGFTLE	DVWDSWPL	QNA	110
tr A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	KIPQQQ--NSDQFEVPAFDESTIKNIIPSAKGDASGNTID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	110
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	KIPQQQ--KSEQFKVPAFDKATIKNIIPSAKGYDKSGNLID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	110
tr A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	KIPQQQ--KSEQFKVPAFDKATIKNIIPSAKGYDKSGNLID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	110
tr A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	KIPEQQ--KNEKYQVPEFDPSSTIKNISSAKG-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	QIPEQQ--KNEKYQVPEFDSSSTIKNISSAKG-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	QIPEQQ--KNEKYQVPEFDSSSTIKNISSAKG-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	QIPEQQ--KNEKYQVPEFDSSSTIKNISSAKG-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	QIPEQQ--KNEKYQVPEFDQSKIKNISSAKG-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
tr A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	KIPEQQ--KSEQFQVPPQFDAKTIQNIPSAKGYNSGKLLID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	108
tr A0A7Z1B6S1 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI	KIPEQQ--KSEQFKVPPQFDPKTIKNIPSAKGYNKNGELID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	108
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	KIPEQQ--KSEQFKVPPQFDPKTIKNIPSAKGYNKNGELID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	108
tr A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	KIPEQQ--KSEQFKVPPQFDPKTIKNIPSAKGYNKNGELID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	108
tr A0A089MVC7 A0A089MVC7_9BACL	KIPEQQ--KSGQFQVPAFNAASIQNISSAKGSDQWGNALID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	110
tr A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	KLPEQQ--KSQFQVPPQFDASTIKNIIPSAIKYDQWGNQID	DVWDTWPL	QNA	109
tr A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL	KLPKQQ--NSRQFQVPPQFDASTIENIPAAIKFDENGNKIEM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	112
tr A0A222K7W7 A0A222K7W7_9BACL	KLPEQQ--KSEQFKVPSFDASTIKNIIPSAIKVDESGNPIEM	DVWDTWPL	QNA	110
tr E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	QIPGQQ--SSAQFEVPEFDASTLKNLH-VQGPDENGNPV	DVWDSWPL	QSP	106
tr A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	KIPGQQ--NSAQFKVPPQFDPSSTIKNIIPAAK-----	LDVWDSWPL	QNA	101
tr A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	KIPEQE--NSAQFKVPPQFDASTLKNILTAKGYDEAGNLID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	109
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	KIPAQQ--NNAQFKVPPQFDASTLKNIPSAKGYDEAGNLID	DVWDSWPL	QNG	109
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	KISEQQ--NNAQFKVPPQFDASTLKNIPSAKGYDEFGNLIN	DVWDSWPL	QNA	109
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	KIPGQQ--NNAQFKVPPQFDASTIKNISSAKDYDKYGNLID	DVWDSWPL	QNA	109
	.. : * . : ** * : : * : .		**** : **	

tr A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	EWSGSALFTDDGELRLFYTNRGRD FDE SKE -LFGROLT	TTAQVNVSEKGDKDLQVDGIEDH	227
tr A0AAX2EH38 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	EWSGSAAFI-DGEIRLFYTNRGG FDE SQG -IFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEKDTSSLQVDGVEDY	230
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	EWSGSAAFI-DGEIRLFYTNRGG FDE SQG -IFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEKDTSSLQVDGVEDY	230
tr A0A084GGQ0 A0A084GGQ0_METID	EWSGSATFTEDGKVRFLFYTNREP FTPESEG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPQSKSLKIDGVEDY	230
tr A0A6I2MEF7 A0A6I2MEF7_9BACI	EWSGSATFTADGKVRFLFYTNREP FTPESEG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPQSKSLKIDGVEDY	230
tr A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNREP FTPESEK -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEKDSSTLNDGVEDY	229
tr A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	EWSGSATFTDDGKVRFLFYTNREP FTPESEG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEPDNTLNDGVEDY	230
tr A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	EWSGSATFTEDGKVRFLFYTNREP FTPESEG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEEAAGTLKIDGVEDY	230
tr A0A926NJ10 A0A926NJ10_9BACI	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTSRQKMEPEAG -YYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDSTTLKVEGVEDY	220
tr A0A1G8FSH7 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNREP FTPESEK -LYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEPEAGTLQVDGVEDH	230
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNREP FTPESEK -LYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEPEAGTLQVDGVEDH	230
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNREP FTPESEK -LYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEPEAGTLQVDGVEDH	230
tr A0A1R1RM81 A0A1R1RM81_9BACI	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTNRHPWDGE -K -HLGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDF	229
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	EWSGSAAALFTDDGKVRFLFYTNRHPWDGE -R -FFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDF	229
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTNRHPWDPAH -FFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	230
tr A0A2N0Z5D7 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTNRHPWDPAH -FFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	230
tr A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNREP FTPESEK -FFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSKLDANTLKIDGVEDH	224
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTNRSD -R -RQMGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPSSTLKLKIDGVEDH	230
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTFSGAPQDGGTGYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEPNAGTIQVDGVEDH	230
tr A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTFYSG -K -QY G KQLT	TTAQVNVSPDNTLKV DGVEDY	224
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTFYSG -T -NYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPSADTLKIDGVEDH	224
tr A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTFYSG -A -NYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPSADTLKIDGVEDH	224
tr A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTFYSG -K -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSTSDS -SLNIDGVEDY	214
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTFYSG -K -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSASDS -SLNINGVEDY	214
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTFYSG -K -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSASDS -SLNINGVEDY	214SDM
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTFYSG -K -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSASDS -SLNINGVEDY	214
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTFYSG -K -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSTSDS -SLNINGVEDY	214
tr A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTFYSG -T -QY G KQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDY	222
tr A0A7Z1B6S1 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI	EWSGSATLTKDQKVRFLFYTFYSG -T -QY G KQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	222
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	EWSGSATLTKDQKVRFLFYTFYSG -T -QY G KQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	222
tr A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	EWSGSATLTKDQKVRFLFYTFYSG -T -QY G KQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	222
tr A0A089MVCV7 A0A089MVCV7_9BACI	EWSGSATLTKDQKVRFLFYTNRHPWDPAH -FFGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDL	229
tr A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	EWSGSATFTSDGKIRLFYTNRHPWAPERG -FYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDF	228
tr A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACI	EWSGSATMTSDGKIRLFYTNRHPWDRG -FYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDM	231
tr A0A222K7W7 A0A222K7W7_9BACL	EWSGSATMTSDGKIRLFYTNRHPWDRG -FYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDF	229
tr E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	EWSGSATLTDANKVRFLFYTRGAFDLANG -LYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDASTIKVDGVDL	224
tr A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTRHSAQDGGSGLGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDH	221
tr A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTRHSLAPERG -FTGKQLT	TTAQVNVSKSDDDTLKIDGVEDL	228
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	EWSGSATLTDGKVRFLFYTRDSDSIETG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDL	228
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	EWSGSATLTS DGEVRLFYTRDSDWAPDSG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSEANANTLKV DGVEDL	228
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	EWSGSATLTKDQKVRFLFYTRDSDWAPDSG -HYGKQLT	TTAQVNVSPDADTLKIDGVEDY	229

tr A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	KSIFNGGDGKTYENVE-KAFEDR---NFN	NHTRDPHYIEDKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	282
tr A0AAX2EH38 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	KSIIYDGGNGKTYENVN-KAFEDR---NFA	NHTRDPHYIEDKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	KSIIYDGGNGKTYENVN-KAFEDR---NFA	NHTRDPHYIEDKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A084GGQ0 A0A084GGQ0_METID	KSIIYEGKDSKYQTV-D-KAFKDG---APN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A6I2MEF7 A0A6I2MEF7_9BACI	KSIIYEGKDSKYQTV-D-KFVBDG---APN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	KSIFEGGDSKMYQTV-D-KAFGGG---DYN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	284
tr A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	KSIIYEGGDSKYQTV-D-KAFGGG---DFS	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	KSIIYEGGDSKYQTV-D-KAFGEG---NFA	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A926NJ10 A0A926NJ10_9BACI	KTIFDG-DGKYQTV-D-QAFNGG---DYS	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	274
tr A0A1G8FSH7 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	KSIFEGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFNGG---NFA	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	KSIFEGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFNGG---DWN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	KSIFEGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFNGG---DWN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr A0A1R1RM81 A0A1R1RM81_9BACI	KSIFEGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFSEG---NFM	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	284
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	KSIFEGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFSDG---NFM	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	284
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	KSIFDG-DGKIYQTV-D-QAFNGG---DYS	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	284
tr A0A2N0Z5D7 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI	KSIIYDGGDSKYQTV-D-KAFGEG---NYA	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	KSIIYDGGDSKYQTV-D-QAFSGG---NYA	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	KSIFAG-DGQYQTV-D-QFIDQGGF---QTG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	279
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	KSIIYDGGDSKYQTV-D-GFIDAGAY---NSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	KSIFDG-DGKIYQTV-D-QFIDEGGY---DTG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	280
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	KSIFDG-DGKYYQTV-D-QFIDEGAY---GSE	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	280
tr A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	KSIFDG-DGKYYQTV-D-QFIDEGAY---GSE	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	280
tr A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	270
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	270
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	270SDM
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	270
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	270
tr A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	279
tr A0A7Z1B6S1 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	279
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	279
tr A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	279
tr A0A089MVCV7 A0A089MVCV7_9BACI	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGNY---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	283
tr A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	KSIIYEGGDSKYQTV-D-KAFGEG---DYN	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	283
tr A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACI	KSIIYDGNQGEIYQTV-D-TGFSKGDY---DND	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr A0A222K7W7 A0A222K7W7_9BACL	KSIIYDGNQGEIYQTV-D-TGFSKGDY---DND	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	KSIFDGGDSKYQTV-D-QGVF---TPG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	277
tr A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	KSIFDGGDSKYQTV-D-QFKDEGLW---GSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	278
tr A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	KSIFDGGDSKYQTV-D-QFID---NSL	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	281
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	KSIFDGGDSKYQTV-D-QFVQASDPSTNTW	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	287
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	KSIFDGGDSKYQTV-D-QFIDEGAD---LSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	KSIFDG-DGKTYQTV-D-QFIDEGKW---SSG	NHTRDPHYIEEDGKGYLVFEANTGTEYG	285

	Hydrolytic module ←	→ Transferase module	
tr A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	402
tr A0AAX2RH38 A0AAX2RH38_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A004GQ0 A0A004GQ0_METID	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A612MEF7 A0A612MEF7_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	404
tr A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A926NJI0 A0A926NJI0_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	394
tr A0A1G8FSH7 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr A0A1R1RM01 A0A1R1RM01_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	404
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	404
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	404
tr A0A2N0Z5D7 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	400
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	400
tr A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	400
tr A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	390
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	390
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	390
tr A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr A0A7Z1B6S1 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	399
tr A0A089MCV7 A0A089MCV7_9BACL	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	403
tr A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	403
tr A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr A0A22K7W7 A0A22K7W7_9BACL	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	397
tr A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	398
tr A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	401
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	407
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	LIVSNTVTTDEERFN	IFPKKDCQWLPFISGSGSMTIDGIDDEDIYM	405

End of levansucrases and family GH68 fructosyl transferases

r A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	IKNKKSVVVDGTLGQGIITYDQ	486
r A0AAX2EH38 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	IDGKRSSVVEDGILEQGIITYEE	489
r A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	IDGKRSSVVEDGILEQGIITYDE	488
r A0A084GQ0 A0A084GQ0_METID	IKGNKTSVVKDSILEQGIITDDE	488
r A0A612MEF7 A0A612MEF7_9BACI	IKGNKTSVVKDSILEQGIITDDE	486
r A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	IKGPHTSVVKDSILNQGQLTID	485
r A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	IKGPNTSVVENSILEQGIITNK	487
r A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	IEGPKTSVVENGILEQGIITINE	488
r A0A926NJI0 A0A926NJI0_9BACI	IKGSKTSVVEDSILEQGIISVNDDEDDDDDDKE	489
r A0A1G8FSH7 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	LKGGKSSVVEDSILEQGIITVDE	490
r A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	LNGKSSVVGDSILEQGIITVDE	490
r A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	LNGKSSVVEDSILEQGIITVDE	490
r A0A1R1RM01 A0A1R1RM01_9BACI	IKGPKTSVVKDSILEQGIITINE	487
r A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	IKGPKTSVVEDGILEQGIITISE	487
r A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	IKGHKTSVVKNSILEQGIITIK	486
r A0A2N0Z5D7 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI	IKGNKTSVVKNSILEQGIITINDKTKKKNR	498
r A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	IKGNKTSVVKNSILEQGIITIK	487
r A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	IDGDETTVVKDSILEQGLQVSKNKQGYGFNKR	493
r A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	IKGSNTSIEKDSILEQGIITVDSQDKK	494
r A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	IDGSKTSVVKDSVLEQGIITVDED	484
r A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	IKGSKTAVVKNSVLEQGIITADK	483
r A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	IKGSKTAVVKNSILEQGIITADK	483
r A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	IKGKTSVVKDSILEQGIITVNK	473
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	IQQKTSVVKASILDQGIITVNG	473
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	IKGKTSVVKDSILEQGIITVNK	473
r B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	IKGKTSVVKDSILEQGIITVNK	473
r A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	IKGKTSVVKDSILEQGIITVNK	473
r A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	VKGSKTSVVKNSILEQGIITVNE	482
r A0A7Z1B6S1 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI	VKGSKTSVVKNSILEQGIITVNE	481
r B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	IKGSKTSVVKNSILEQGIITVNK	482
r A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	IKGSKTSVVKNSILEQGIITVNK	482
r A0A089MCV7 A0A089MCV7_9BACL	IKGSKTSVVKDSVLEQGIITVTK	485
r A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	IEGSKTSVVPNSILEQGIITIDK	486
r A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL	IKGSKTSVVPNSILEQGIITLKGKPKY	494
r A0A22K7W7 A0A22K7W7_9BACL	IKGSKTSVVKDSILEQGIITIDQKKNK	496
r E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	ILGNHTSVVQGLLAQGIITIDGQHRR	485
r A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	INGPKTSVVPSSILEQGIITADK	481
r A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	IKDSKTSVVENSTLEQGIITIDK	484
r A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	IQQKTSVVPNSILEQGIITIDK	490
r R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	IKGDKTSVVPNSILEQGIITIDKENTFNK	495
r R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	IKGSKTSVVPNSILEQGIITVTK	488

A0A163L384_9BACI Levansucrase, *Rossellomorea marisflavi*
 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI Levansucrase, *Terribacillus saccharophilus*
 A0A268AGA6_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Terribacillus saccharophilus*
 A0A084GQG0_METID Levansucrase, *Metabacillus indicus*
 A0A612MEF7_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Metabacillus idriensis*
 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI Levansucrase, *Fictibacillus solisalsi*
 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI Levansucrase, *Domibacillus enclensis*
 A0AA96N005_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Domibacillus sp.*
 A0A926NJI0_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Metabacillus arenae*
 A0AA90JC76_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Bacillus haynesii*
 A0A926S2X1_9BACI GH68 family protein, *Metabacillus arenae*
 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI Levansucrase, *Alteribacillus bidgolensis*
 A0A428MZE4_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Salibacterium salarium*
 A0A917B9N0_HALAA Levansucrase, *Halobacillus andaensis*
 A0A1R1RM81_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Bacillus swezeyi*
 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI Levansucrase, *Evansella caseinilytica*
 A0A2N0Z5D7_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Niallia nealsonii*
 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI GH 68 family protein, *Niallia circulans*
 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Metabacillus mangrovi*
 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI Levansucrase, *Bacillus gobiensis*
 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG GH 68 family protein, *Priestia megaterium*
 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG Levansucrase, *Priestia megaterium*
 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR GH 68 family protein, *Priestia aryabhatai*
 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA Levansucrase, *Bacillus vallismortis*
 P94468L_SCI_GEOSE Inactive levansucrase, *Geobacillus stearothermophilus, sacB*
 P05655LSC_BACSU Levansucrase, *Bacillus subtilis, sacB*
 B0N5W2_9FIRM Levansucrase, *Thomasclavelia ramosa*
 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC Levansucrase, *Bacillus spizizenii*
 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Bacillus swezeyi*
 A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Bacillus paralicheniformis*
 B6DVC6_BACLI Levansucrase, *Bacillus licheniformis*
 A0AA96N005_9BACI GH 68 family protein, *Domibacillus sp*
 A0A089MCV7_9BACL Levansucrase, *Paenibacillus graminis*
 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT GH 68 family protein, *Clostridium polyendosporum*
 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL GH 68 family protein, *Paenibacillus odorifer*
 A0A2Z2K7W7_9BACL GH 68 family protein, *Paenibacillus donghaensis*
 E6U567_ETHHY GH 68 family protein, *Ethanoligenens harbinense*
 A0A917S1W0_9BACL GH 68 family protein, *Sporolactobacillus putidus*
 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA Levansucrase, *Clostridium saccharobutylicum*
 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA Levansucrase, *Clostridium pasteurianum*
 R4K9X0_CLOPA Levansucrase, *Clostridium pasteurianum*
 R4K861_CLOPA Levansucrase, *Clostridium pasteurianum*

Figure 1 MSA of levansucrases and GH68 family glycoside hydrolase fructosyl transferases

3.2. MSA analysis of inulosucrases

Figure 2 shows the MSA of inulosucrases from different bacteria, (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). These are also bifunctional enzymes like the levansucrases and exhibit two different activities, viz. hydrolytic and transferase activities. The active site amino acids of hydrolytic and transferase domains are highlighted in yellow and green, respectively. Like the levansucrases, the inulosucrases are also composed of the same catalytic triad. The N-terminal is not conserved among them until it reaches the first catalytic site amino acid, D (nucleophile). The catalytic triad is found in the completely conserved motifs, the nucleophilic amino acid D is found in -WDSW-. The proposed Glc-binding motif is the conserved, -WSGSA- motif. In the other two highly conserved motifs, one harbours the acid-base catalytic amino acid E, -EI/VER- and the other is the proposed Fru-binding motif, -M/LRDP/AH-, where the -RD- pair is found invariant in all and shown to involve in catalysis by SDM. As found in the levansucrases, the catalytic triad in the second transferase domain of inulosucrases is also highly conserved, viz. the basic amino acid, K/R for proton abstraction, and a completely conserved fructose donor selection amino acid, R at -3, and a template-binding pair, -MI//VLG- at -22 from the proton abstractor and usually exists as a conserved triad. Interestingly, the active site amino acids in the transferase domain are the same as the nucleotidyl transferase domain found in the DNA/ RNA polymerases [1-3]. Most of the inulosucrases' active site amino acids are also confirmed by SDM experiments and X-ray crystallographic data. For example, in *Lactobacillus reuteri* the catalytic triad is composed of D²⁷², E⁵²³ and D⁴²⁴ (highlighted) and also confirmed by SDM analysis. The other three completely conserved residues, viz. W²⁷¹, W³⁴⁰ and R⁴²³ (highlighted) are located at the -1 subsite. Inulosucrase mutants W³⁴⁰→N and R⁴²³→H were virtually inactive, confirming the essential role played by these residues in the inulosucrase active site [29, 30].

SYW17616.1	TFDQDWQNSSYAYPEIDSSKVENLSAADMVSDSTPNVTTEGEVDTQAVQLDVS	WDSW	PLQNAQ	270
EOD02545.1	AKKIVNRDSSSQIPLFKGEKIVNMPGLEKVKD---AE---TGEEATMDI	WDSW	PPVQDPE	328
tr Q7X481 Q7X481_LEUCI	IKLAQKPPDKTTIPVFNASQINNLPA--IFKD---AQ---TNKVEKMDV	WDSW	ALQDSK	363
XAO78497.1	ADKLAEVDPQYAIPIYFKADQIQNLPA--TAKD---GQ---TGKVANMDI	WDSW	PPVQDPT	329
VTY24076.1	VASFLKQDSKLAVPYFKADTIINMPAF--NTVD---AQ---TMEKEEIDV	WDSW	PPVQDAE	288
VUW83976.1	VASFLKQDSKLAVPYFKADTIINMPAF--NTVD---AQ---TMEKEEIDV	WDSW	PPVQDAE	288
VTY27523.1	VASFLKQDSKLAVPYFKADTIINMPAF--NTVD---AQ---TMEKEEIDV	WDSW	PPVQDAK	295
VTY49811.1	AQTLIAQDERYAIPIYFNAKAIKNMKA--TTRD---AQ---TGQIADLDV	WDSW	PPVQDAK	254
CAH1856476.1	ADSLVDRDQRYAVPVFDAGKIENLPA--YSRD---AQ---TGQYEHLDI	WDSW	PPVQNPQ	251
pdb 8XVQ B	ADTLIKQDGRYTVPPFKASEIKNMPAA--TTKD---AQ---TNTIEPLDV	WDSW	PPVQDVR	280
WVT67746.1	ADTLIKQDGRYTVPPFKASEIKNMPAA--TTKD---AQ---TNTIEPLDV	WDSW	PPVQDVR	280
tr Q8GP32 Q8GP32_LIMRT	ADTLIKQDGRYTVPPFKASEIKNMPAA--TTKD---AQ---TNTIEPLDV	WDSW	PPVQDVR	280SDM
GFI19642.1	AKTLIEQDARYAIPFNASKIKNMPAA--KTLD---AQ---SGKVEDEI	WDSW	PPVQDAK	280
ACZ67286.1	AKTLIEQDARYAVPPFNASKIKNMPAA--KTLD---AQ---TGKVEDEI	WDSW	PPVQDAK	274

SYW17616.1	DVDYTYGVNQDTASAWGANPLVQDSNLSFHENQFVEAEQ	WGS	AVLNSDNIQLYYSV	390
EOD02545.1	-----NDPSTGQ	WGS	SAMLNADGSIQLFYTDV	407
tr Q7X481 Q7X481_LEUCI	-----AKPESQEW	WGS	AVVNSDDSIQLFYTRV	443SDM
XAO78497.1	DKKT-----GLEIFGDQ	WGS	AVPLDDGSIQLFYTHS	416
VTY24076.1	-----ALEDDQ	WGS	AVVNSDGSIQLFYTMN	367
VUW83976.1	-----ALEDDQ	WGS	AVVNSDGSIQLFYTMN	367
VTY27523.1	-----ALEDDQ	WGS	AVVNSDGSIQLYYTKN	374
VTY49811.1	-----ETPLTQ	WGS	AVVNEGSLQLFYTKV	333
CAH1856476.1	-----ASPLSQ	WGS	AVVNPDDSIQMFYTOV	330
pdb 8XVQ B	-----STAVSQ	WGS	AVVNSDNSIQLFYTRV	359
WVT67746.1	-----STAVSQ	WGS	AVVNSDNSIQLFYTRV	359
tr Q8GP32 Q8GP32_LIMRT	-----STAVSQ	WGS	AVVNSDNSIQLFYTRV	359SDM
GFI19642.1	-----T-PVIQ	WGS	AVVTLNKDGSIQLYYTKV	358
ACZ67286.1	-----T-PVIQ	WGS	AVVTLNKDGSIQLYYTKV	352

SYW17616.1	NKQIFDYESQ-EKNGE--PQVLNG	MRDPH	VIIV-NGQRYLAFESTTLVDNG--QGIVED	489
EOD02545.1	FSQWQNGTN-----SSVNNPQ	MRDAH	IFKDSGTYIYAFETATGDLGDDEAES--AH	502
tr Q7X481 Q7X481_LEUCI	KDQLK-----QADMFL	MRDPK	LIELDDGERYLTFEANTGIYDE--ASD--Q	530
XAO78497.1	FDQWAHNVTFMDGHKEDFGGADNFAMRDPH	IVKDSQGNRYLVFEASTGDDY--Q	530	
VTY24076.1	YPKFMDTFNDDHNDGIPDRADNYCLRDPH	IED-KGSRYLIFESNTGDENY--QGE-KQ	470	
VUW83976.1	YPKFMDTFNDDHNDGIPDRADNYCLRDPH	IED-KGSRYLIFESNTGDENY--QGE-KQ	470	
VTY27523.1	YPKFMDTFDDHNDGPNDRDNYCLRDPH	IED-NGSRYLIFESNTGDENY--QGE-KQ	477	
VTY49811.1	YQQRSTFT-----GADNIAM	MRDPH	VIDENGDRLVFEASTGTENY--QGE-DQ	429
CAH1856476.1	YPOWRATNQ-----GADNIAL	RDSH	VDDADGSRYLIFEGATGSONY--QGE-HQ	424
pdb 8XVQ B	YDQWKATNK-----GADNIAM	MRDAH	VIDDNGDRYLVFEASTGLENY--QGE-DQ	453
WVT67746.1	YDQWKATNK-----GADNIAM	MRDAH	VIDDNGDRYLVFEASTGLENY--QGE-DQ	453
tr Q8GP32 Q8GP32_LIMRT	YDQWKATNK-----GADNIAM	MRDAH	VIDDNGDRYLVFEASTGLENY--QGE-DQ	453SDM
GFI19642.1	YDQWKATNK-----GADNIAM	MRDAH	VIDDNGDRYLVFEASTGTENY--QGD-DQ	454
ACZ67286.1	YNQWKATNK-----GADNIAM	MRDAH	VIDDKDGNYLVFEASTGTENY--QGA-DQ	448

SYW17616.1	E---NNNVT-----VVL	PIITATMASTEIER	PSI	VFMNGRYLFFVATV	SSIDD	582	
EOD02545.1	MSDPKNPQVATDENGKLVLYRPLVKT	VLSGDEVER	PDL	IKLNGKYYLFTDGR	LTRATD	606	
tr Q7X481 Q7X481_LEUCI	G-DYFNPILD-----RLYK	PLITAVGV	TEIER	ANI	VPFNGRYLFTDS	RFNRSAADN	626
XAO78497.1	G-TENNPTVA-----EYVD	PIISAVM	VSDIEIER	PDI	VKIGDTYYLFAAS	RLNRGTNDA	642
VTY24076.1	D-NEKNPSVA-----ELYT	PLVTS	SHMVTDEVER	PSV	VKMGNRYLFAAS	RLNRSTDAE	566
VUW83976.1	D-NEKNPSVA-----ELYT	PLVTS	SHMVTDEVER	PSV	VKMGNRYLFAAS	RLNRSTDAE	566
VTY27523.1	D-NEKNPSVA-----ELYT	PLVTS	SHMVTDEVER	PSV	VKMGGRYLFTAS	RINKSTDAE	573
VTY49811.1	G-DKKTPEVD-----QFYT	PLLS	STMVSDIEIER	PNV	VKLGDRYYLFTAS	RLNRGSNND	525
CAH1856476.1	D-QGKTPTVA-----QLYT	PLITAN	MVSDIEIER	PDV	VKIGGRYYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDY	520
pdb 8XVQ B	K-DEKNPKVA-----ELYS	PLISAP	MVSDIEIER	PNV	VKLGNYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDD	549
WVT67746.1	K-DEKNPKVA-----ELYS	PLISAP	MVSDIEIER	PNV	VKLGNYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDD	549
tr Q8GP32 Q8GP32_LIMRT	K-DEKNPKVA-----ELYS	PLISAP	MVSDIEIER	PNV	VKLGNYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDD	549SDM
GFI19642.1	D-DVKNPSVA-----KVYS	PLISAP	MVSDIEIER	PDV	VKLGNYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDD	550
ACZ67286.1	N-DTRKNPGE-----KYVT	PLISAP	MVSDIEIER	PDV	VRLGNRYLFAA	TRLNRGSNDD	544

SYW17616.1 putative Inulosucrase, *Oenococcus oeni*
 EOD02545.1 Inulosucrase InuJ, *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*
 Q7X481_LEUCI Inulosucrase, *Leuconostoc citreum*
 XAO78497.1 Inulosucrase, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*
 VTY24076.1 Inulosucrase, *Streptococcus salivarius*
 VUW83976.1 Inulosucrase, *Streptococcus thermophilus*
 VTY27523.1 Inulosucrase, *Streptococcus salivarius*
 VTY49811.1 Inulosucrase, *Streptococcus mutans*
 CAH1856476.1 Inulosucrase, *Convivina intestini*
 8XVQ|B Chain B, Inulosucrase
 WVT67746.1 Sequence 14 from patent US 11859216
 Q8GP32_LIMRT Inulosucrase, *Limosilactobacillus reuteri*
 GFI19642.1 Inulosucrase, *Lactobacillus johnsonii*
 ACZ67286.1 Inulosucrase, *Lactobacillus gasseri*

Figure 2 MSA of inulosucrases from different bacteria

3.3. 'Mix and Match' MSA analysis of levansucrases, inulosucrases and other Family GH68 fructosyl transferases

Figure 3 shows the 'Mix and Match' MSA of all the enzymes belonging to fructosyl transferases, viz. levansucrases, inulosucrases and other GH68 family glycoside hydrolases, (only the required regions for the discussions are shown). The active site amino acids of the hydrolytic and transferase domains from all three groups are highlighted in yellow and green, respectively. The active and inactive transferase enzyme from *B. subtilis* and *G. stercorophilus* is highlighted in green and red, respectively. Strikingly, all three groups revealed high sequence similarities mostly at their catalytic sites only. Furthermore, it is interesting to note that the enzyme from *S. mutans*, the organism which causes dental caries in humans, synthesizes a β -(1 \rightarrow 2)-linked fructan (inulin type), whereas the *B. subtilis* (a nonpathogenic organism) produces a β -(2 \rightarrow 6)-linked polymer (levan type). As the hydrolytic site amino acids are the same, the structural difference of the fructans may be correlated with the sequence difference(s) around the transferase catalytic regions. For example, the comparison of the active site regions in levan and inulin synthetic enzymes show distinct differences in their distance motifs between the proton donor and the proposed template-binding pair. In fact, a longer distance motif between the proton abstractor and the template-binding pair is observed in inulosucrases of *S. mutans*, (e.g.), *B. subtilis* use, -SR³GSK¹MTIDGITSNDIYML¹⁵GY- and *S. mutans* use, -SR³LNH¹GSNNDAWNKANEEVVGDNVVML²¹GY-). It is interesting to note that in *S. mutans*, the EPS of dental plaque contains approximately 30% inulin, which protects the cells from antimicrobial materials present in saliva by forming biofilm [31].

The inulosucrase sequences start from the light blue highlighted sequence. Interestingly, they are larger proteins, and are almost double the size of the other two groups of transferases. There are big gaps in the N-terminal region and more or less no conserved amino acids or regions (data not shown) are observed until it reaches the first highly conserved tetrapeptide, -WDS/T/W/M-. This tetrapeptide harbours the invariant D, which acts as the catalytic nucleophile in the hydrolytic reaction. Again, there are gaps in the alignment until it reaches the second highly conserved tetrapeptide, -Q/D/EWSG/A- and is suggested to interact with the Glu unit of the sucrose molecule. This is followed by the next conserved tetrapeptide is -MF/LRDP/A/S- which is highly conserved in all three groups suggesting its importance. This tetrapeptide is suggested to interact with the Fru unit of the sucrose molecule. Substitution of Asp³⁰⁹ by Asn in the -FRD³⁰⁹P- motif of *A. diazotrophicus* levansucrase reduced the *k*_{cat} of the mutant enzyme 75-fold, indicating that Asp³⁰⁹ plays a major role in catalysis affecting the overall efficiency of sucrose hydrolysis. It is interesting to note that this tetrapeptide motif is conserved not only in the fructosyltransferases, but also in invertases, levanasases, inulinases and sucrose-6-phosphate hydrolases, suggesting a common functional role for this motif in these enzymes [32]. Yanase *et al.* [33] found that the substitution of Asp¹⁹⁴, located in the -FRD¹⁹⁴P- motif of *Z. mobilis* levansucrase abolished sucrose

hydrolysis, suggesting its importance in catalysis. Furthermore, they found that the His²⁹⁶, in the transferase domain is crucial for catalysis of the transfructosylation reaction –FT³ISH²⁹⁶HSTYADGLSGPDGVY¹⁶GF-. Not much conservation is observed until it reaches the next highly conserved tetrapeptide –QT/EI/VER-. The –ER- pair is completely conserved in all and the invariant -E- is known to act as the acid/base catalyst in the hydrolytic reaction.

Immediately after the hydrolytic module, the transferase active site domain is placed (highlighted in green). It is interesting to note that the transferase module is very similar to the nucleotidyl transferases module found in the DNA/RNA polymerases and composed of a similar catalytic triad, viz. a proton abstractor (usually a basic amino acid in all DNA/RNA polymerases and is conserved in the fructosyl transferases also) and a donor selection amino acid R at -3 to -4 from the proton abstractor and a template-binding pair -L/I/GY or -YG- (a highly conserved -YG- pair is shown as the template-binding pair in most of the DNA/RNA polymerases (Table 2). Interestingly, in all these group of fructosyl transferases a highly conserved template-binding triad, rather than a pair, is observed. The levansucrase from *G. stearothermophilus*, is reported to be inactive. The main difference between the active (from *B. subtilis*) and the inactive (from *G. stearothermophilus*) levansucrases is the proton abstractor, where the K is replaced by Q, respectively (marked in red). As the Q does not act as a proton abstractor in transferases, the enzyme could be inactive which is further confirmed by MSA analysis and SDM data. Interestingly, the same highly conserved amino acids at the catalytic sites of the two different transferases, viz. the fructosyl and nucleotidyl transferases suggest common evolutionary principles in designing active sites for same type of reactions in living cells.

CLUSTAL O (1.2.4) 'Mix and Match' MSA of levan- and inulosucrases and other GH68 family glycoside hydrolase fructosyl transferases.

sp Q43998 LSC_CLUDI	FNIPADF-----FVINFQVWY	NDTI	FLIDK-HADQ----	PSYNGWEVIFCLI	159
tr B2IF79 B2IF79_BEI19	PDIADF-----PQTFQVWY	NDT	FLADV-HGNO----	LSFGQWEVIFSLT	124
tr D0J9C2 D0J9C2_HALJD	PIIYFPR-----EDAFPEING	NDT	FLRER-DGSI----	ATVGGWEVIFSLI	71
tr A0A0M3KKU6 A0A0M3KKU6_ERWAB	PVIDIAT-----FVMSEEVFI	NDT	FLRDF-DGEI----	ISVNGWCIIFTLT	70
tr B2VCC3 B2VCC3_ERWT9	PLVDVAF-----FVMSEEVFI	NDT	FLRDF-DGDI----	VSVNGWCVIFTLT	70
SVW17616.1	ENLGAADMVDTFNVVTEGEVDTQAVOLDV	WDS	SWFLQNAOTGAAQOSITINGKGYQIVIAM		291
tr A0A163L304 A0A163L304_9BACI	KNVESAT-K-----TDESGNLIKMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYKGYHIVFGLA	117
tr A0AAX2MH38 A0AAX2MH38_9BACI	KNIKSAT-K-----IDENGNLIKMDV	NDT	WFLQNF-DGTV----	ADYNGYQIVFGLA	122
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	KNIKSAT-K-----IDENGNVVKMDV	NDT	WFLQNF-DGTV----	ADYNGYQIVFGLA	122
tr A0A084QQ00 A0A084QQ00_METID	ENIPSAK-K-----TTESGETMDLDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYKGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A6I2MEF7 A0A6I2MEF7_9BACI	KNIPSAK-K-----VTESGETIDMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYKGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A1H0C313 A0A1H0C313_9BACI	KNIPSAK-K-----YDKDGNLIKMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYKGYHIVFGLA	119
tr A0A1N8Y262 A0A1N8Y262_9BACI	KNI PAAT-K-----TDENGNTIMMDV	NDT	WFLQNT-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A96N005 A0A96N005_9BACI	KNI PAAO-K-----VDENGNLMDLDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A926NJ10 A0A926NJ10_9BACI	KNIPSAE-G-----LDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYKGYQIVFGLA	110
tr A0A1G0TSH7 A0A1G0TSH7_9BACI	ENIPSAK-K-----INDESGEIDMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	ENIPSAT-K-----TDESGNIEIVMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	DNIPSAT-K-----TDESGNIEIVMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A1R1R001 A0A1R1R001_9BACI	KNIPSAK-K-----YDESGNKIMLDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYKGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	VNI PTAQ-K-----YDESGNIMDI DV	NDT	WFLQTG-DGTV----	AKYNGYHIVFGLA	120
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	KNIPSAK-G-----YDESGNVIDL DV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYNGYQIVFGLA	120
tr A0A2N025D7 A0A2N025D7_9BACI	KNIPSAK-K-----TDESGNVIDL DV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYQIAFGLA	120
tr A0A91TQD8 A0A91TQD8_NTACI	KNI PSAK-G-----YDESGNLI DL DV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYQIVFGLA	120
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	KNIK SAT-G-----YDKDGNLIL DV	NDT	WFLMNA-DGTV----	ADYKGYQIVFGLA	119
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	RNI PTAQ-G-----YDESGNIEIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHLFETLA	119
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_FRIMG	KNIASAK-G-----YDESGNLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTI----	ANYHGYQVVFALA	119
tr A0A9F8K2B5 A0A9F8K2B5_FRIAR	KNIASAK-G-----YDESGNLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYQVVFALA	119
tr A0A3D0X650 A0A3D0X650_FRIMG	KNIASAK-G-----KDA SGNTIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYHGYQVVFALA	119
tr D5DC07 D5DC07_FRIM3	KNIASAK-G-----KNASGNTIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYHGYQVVFALA	119
tr A0A9F3F0J4 A0A9F3F0J4_BACVA	KNIPSAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	110
sp P94460 LSCI_GEOGE	KNIPSAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	110
sp P05655 LSC_BACSC	KNIPSAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	110
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9PIRM	KNIPSAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	110
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	KNIPSAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	110
tr A0A5M0RY49 A0A5M0RY49_9BACI	QNI PSAK-G-----YNSGGKLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYNGYHLVFFALA	117
tr A0A7X1H6S1 A0A7X1H6S1_9BACI	KNI PSAK-G-----YKNGKELIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYHGYHIVFALA	117
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	KNI PSAK-G-----YKNGKELIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYHGYHIVFALA	117
tr A0A903JCT6 A0A903JCT6_9BACI	KNI PSAK-G-----YKNGKELIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ATYHGYHIVFALA	117
tr A0A089MCV7 A0A089MCV7_9BACL	QNI PSAK-G-----SDWGNLIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	AEYNGYHIVFALA	119
tr A0A919RYE9 A0A919RYE9_9CLOT	KNI PSAI-K-----YDWSGNIDL DV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYNGYHIVFGLA	119
tr A0A1R0XBD9 A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL	ENI PAAT-TV-----FDENGNRIEMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ASYKGYQIVFGLA	121
tr A0A22EK7W7 A0A22EK7W7_9BACL	KNI PSAI-K-----VDESGNFIEMDV	NDT	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYNGYHIVFGLA	119
tr E6U567 E6U567_ETHHY	KNLH-VO-G-----FDENGNFVLD DV	WDS	WFLQSF-DGTV----	ATYNGYHLVFFALV	115
tr A0A917S1W0 A0A917S1W0_9BACL	KNI PAAK-G-----LDV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTA----	ANYHGYHLVFFALA	110
tr A0A1S8MP69 A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA	KNI LTAQ-G-----YDEAGNLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYNGYHIVFALA	118
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOFA	KNI PSAK-G-----YDEAGNLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNG-DGTV----	SNYHGYHIVFALA	118
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOFA	KNI PSAK-G-----YDE PGNLIDL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHLVFFALA	118
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOFA	KNI PSAK-D-----YDKYGNLI DL DV	WDS	WFLQNA-DGTV----	ANYHGYHIVFALA	118
K0002545.1	VKNMGLKVK-----DAQTGEEATMDI	WDS	WVQDFE TGYV----	ENWNGYQLVVFAMI	343
KA078497.1	QNL PAAT-AR-----DQQTGRVANMDI	WDS	WVQDFPTTGEI----	ANNWNGQLVVFAM	346
VZY24076.1	INM PAFN-TV-----DAQTMKEEIDV	WDS	WVQDAE SGLV----	SNWNGYQLVVIAMA	305
VUW83976.1	INM PAFN-TV-----DAQTMKEEIDV	WDS	WVQDAE SGLV----	SNWNGYQLVVIAMA	305
VZY27523.1	INM PAFN-TV-----DAQTMKEEIDV	WDS	WVQDAK SGLV----	SNWNGYQLVVIAMA	312
sp Q70XJ9 LSC_FRUSA	KNMPASV-TV-----DAQTGRMAHL DV	WDS	WVQDFE TGYV----	SNYKGYQLVVIAM	336
VZY49811.1	KNMPAAT-TV-----DAQTGRMAHL DV	WDS	WVQDFE TGYV----	SNYKGYQLVVIAM	271
CAM1056476.1	ENL PAAV-SR-----DAQTGRVYHLLD	WDS	WVQDFPOTGEV----	VNWHGYQLVVFAM	260
CAM1056006.1	QNF PAAV-TR-----DAQNTI VEHLDI	WDS	WVQNFYTGQV----	SNWNGYQLVVFAM	254
pdb 9XV0 B	KNMPAAT-TV-----DAQNTI EPL DV	WDS	WVQDVRTGQV----	ANNWNGYQLVVIAM	297
VWT67746.1	KNMPAAT-TV-----DAQNTI EPL DV	WDS	WVQDVRTGQV----	ANNWNGYQLVVIAM	297
tr Q8GP32 Q8GP32_LIMRT	KNMPAAT-TV-----DAQNTI EPL DV	WDS	WVQDVRTGQV----	ANNWNGYQLVVIAM	297
sp I5642.1	KNMPAAK-TL-----DAQSGKVELEI	WDS	WVQDAKTGYV----	SNWNGYQLVVIAM	297
AC267286.1	KNMPAAK-TL-----DAQTGRVEDLEI	WDS	WVQDAKTGYV----	SNWNGYQLVVIAM	291

/End of levan- inulosucrases and family GH68 fructosyl transferases		
sp Q43998 LSC_GLUDI	-----	534
tr B2IF78 B2IF78_BEII9	-----	534
tr D8J9C2 D8J9C2_HALJB	-----	428
tr A0A0M3KKU6 A0A0M3KKU6_ERWAE	-----	415
tr B2VCC3 B2VCC3_ERWT9	-----	415
SYW17616.1	KRSNGMYTYAQLDGNKTYWIDQRALSTKKK	1164
tr A0A163L384 A0A163L384_9BACI	-----	436
tr A0AAX2EH38 A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	-----	439
tr A0A268AGA6 A0A268AGA6_9BACI	-----	438
tr A0A084GQG0 A0A084GQG0_METID	-----	438
tr A0A6I2MEF7 A0A6I2MEF7_9BACI	-----	436
tr A0A1H0C3I3 A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	-----	435
tr A0A1N6Y262 A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	-----	437
tr A0AA96N005 A0AA96N005_9BACI	-----	436
tr A0A926NJI0 A0A926NJI0_9BACI	-----	439
tr A0A1G8FSH7 A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	-----	490
tr A0A428MZE4 A0A428MZE4_9BACI	-----	490
tr A0A917B9N0 A0A917B9N0_HALAA	-----	490
tr A0A1R1RM81 A0A1R1RM81_9BACI	-----	437
tr A0A1H3V2M3 A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	-----	437
tr A0A926S2X1 A0A926S2X1_9BACI	-----	436
tr A0A2N0ZSD7 A0A2N0ZSD7_9BACI	-----	498
tr A0AA91TQD8 A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	-----	437
tr A0A7X2V5Z1 A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	-----	493
tr A0A0M3RAN0 A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	-----	494
tr A0A806U3J9 A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	-----	433
tr A0AAP8K2B5 A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	-----	433
tr A0A3D8X658 A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	-----	434
tr D5DC07 D5DC07_PRIM3	-----	434
tr A0AAP3FQJ4 A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	-----	473
sp P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	-----	473
sp P05655 LSC_BACSU	-----	473
tr B0N5W2 B0N5W2_9FIRM	-----	473
tr A0A9Q4DMY4 A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC	-----	473
tr A0A5M8RY49 A0A5M8RY49_9BACI	-----	432
tr A0A721B6S1 A0A721B6S1_9BACI	-----	431
tr B6DVC6 B6DVC6_BACLI	-----	432
tr A0AA90JC76 A0AA90JC76_9BACI	-----	432
tr A0A089MCV7 A0A089MCV7_9BACI	-----	435
tr A0A919RYE8 A0A919RYE8_9CLOT	-----	436
tr A0A1ROXBD9 A0A1ROXBD9_9BACI	-----	494
tr A0A222K7W7 A0A222K7W7_9BACI	-----	496
tr E6U567 E6U567_EPHH1	-----	435
tr A0A917B1W0 A0A917B1W0_9BACI	-----	431
tr A0A188MP69 A0A188MP69_CLOSA	-----	434
tr A0A0H3J026 A0A0H3J026_CLOPA	-----	490
tr R4K9X0 R4K9X0_CLOPA	-----	435
tr R4K861 R4K861_CLOPA	-----	435
P0D02545.1	-----	1023
KAO78497.1	-----	957
VTY24076.1	-----	955
VUW82976.1	-----	955
VTY27523.1	-----	969
sp Q70XJ9 LSC_FRUSA	-----	979
VTY49811.1	-----	795
CAH1856476.1	-----	663
CAH1856006.1	-----	734
pdb 8XVQ1B	-----	793
WVZ67746.1	-----	793
tr Q86FP32 Q86FP32_LIMRT	-----	793
GFI19642.1	-----	303
ACC267286.1	-----	761

NB: The SDM and X-ray crystallographic data are highlighted in dark blue and light blue in bold, respectively.

B2IF78_BEII9	Levansucrase, <i>Beijerinckia indica</i>
D8J9C2_HALJB	Levansucrase, <i>Halalkalicoccus jeotgali</i>
A0A0M3KKU6_ERWAE	levansucrase, <i>Erwinia amylovora</i>
B2VCC3_ERWT9	levansucrase, <i>Erwinia tasmaniensis</i>
SYW17616.1	putative Inulosucrase, <i>Oenococcus oeni</i>
A0A163L384_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Rosellomorea marisflavi</i>
A0AAX2EH38_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Terribacillus saccharophilus</i>
A0A268AGA6_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Terribacillus saccharophilus</i>
A0A084GQG0_METID	Levansucrase, <i>Metabacillus indicus</i>
A0A6I2MEF7_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Metabacillus idriensis</i>
A0A1H0C3I3_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Fictibacillus solisalsi</i>
A0A1N6Y262_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Domibacillus enclensis</i>
A0AA96N005_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Domibacillus</i> sp.
A0A926NJI0_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Metabacillus arenae</i>
A0A1G8FSH7_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Alteribacillus bidgolensis</i>
A0A428MZE4_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Salibacterium salarium</i>
A0A917B9N0_HALAA	Levansucrase, <i>Halobacillus andoensis</i>
A0A1R1RM81_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Bacillus swazeyi</i>
A0A1H3V2M3_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Evansella caseinilytica</i>
A0A926S2X1_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Metabacillus arenae</i>
A0A2N0ZSD7_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Niallia nealsonii</i>
A0AA91TQD8_NIACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Niallia circularis</i>
A0A7X2V5Z1_9BACI	GH68 family protein, <i>Metabacillus mangrovi</i>
A0A0M3RAN0_9BACI	Levansucrase, <i>Bacillus gobiensis</i>
A0A806U3J9_PRIMG	Levansucrase, <i>Priestia megaterium</i>
A0AAP8K2B5_PRIAR	GH68 family protein, <i>Priestia aryabhatai</i>
A0A3D8X658_PRIMG	GH68 family protein, <i>Priestia (Bacillus) megaterium</i>
D5DC07_PRIM3	Levansucrase, <i>Priestia (Bacillus) megaterium</i>
A0AAP3FQJ4_BACVA	Levansucrase, <i>Bacillus vallismortis</i>
P94468 LSCI_GEOSE	inactive levansucrase, <i>Geobacillus stearothermophilus</i>, sacB
P05655 LSC_BACSU	Levansucrase, <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>, sacB

```

B0N5W2_9FIRM Levansucrase, Thomasclavelia ramosa
A0A9Q4DMY4_BACSC Levansucrase, Bacillus spizizenii
A0A5M8RY49_9BACI GH68 family protein, Bacillus swezeyi
B6DVC6_BACLI Levansucrase, Bacillus licheniformis
A0AA90JC76_9BACI GH68 family protein, Bacillus haynesii
A0A089MCV7_9BACL Levansucrase, Paenibacillus graminis
A0A919RYE8_9CLOT GH68 family protein, Clostridium polyendosporum
A0A1R0XBD9_9BACL GH68 family protein, Paenibacillus odorifer
A0A2Z2K7W7_9BACL GH68 family protein, Paenibacillus donghaensis
E6U567_ETHHY GH68 family protein, Ethanoligenens harbinense
A0A917S1W0_9BACL GH68 family protein, Sporolactobacillus putidus
A0A1S8MP69_CLOSA Levansucrase, Clostridium saccharobutylicum
A0A0H3J026_CLOPA Levansucrase, Clostridium pasteurianum
A0A7Z1B6S1_9BACI GH68 family protein, Bacillus paraticheniformis
R4K9X0_CLOPA Levansucrase/Invertase, Clostridium pasteurianum
R4K861_CLOPA Levansucrase/Invertase, Clostridium pasteurianum
EOD02545.1 Inulosucrase InuJ, Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. jacobsenii
XAO78497.1 Inulosucrase, Lactiplantibacillus plantarum
VTY24076.1 Inulosucrase, Streptococcus salivarius
VUW83976.1 Inulosucrase, Streptococcus thermophilus
VTY27523.1 Inulosucrase, Streptococcus salivarius
Q70XJ9LSC_FRUSA Levansucrase, Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis
VTY49811.1 Inulosucrase, Streptococcus mutans
CAH1856476.1 Inulosucrase, Cornivina intestini
CAH1856006.1 Inulosucrase, Cornivina praedatoris
pdb|8XVQ|B Chain B, Inulosucrase
WVT67746.1 Sequence 14 from patent US 11859216
Q8GP32_LIMRT Inulosucrase, Limosilactobacillus reuteri
GFI19642.1 Inulosucrase, Lactobacillus johnsonii
ACZ67286.1 Inulosucrase, Lactobacillus gasseri

```

Figure 3 'Mix and Match' MSA of all three groups of fructosyl transferases: levansucrases, inulosucrases and GH68 family glycoside hydrolases from Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria

4. Analyses of active site amino acids in the hydrolytic and transferase domains

The amino acids in the hydrolytic and transferase active sites are confirmed by SDM experiments, X-ray crystallographic and MSA analyses. All three groups, viz. the levansucrases, inulosucrases and other GH68 family of glycoside hydrolases invariably use three highly conserved amino acids in their active sites, as catalytic triad, for hydrolysis of sucrose molecule and another catalytic triad for subsequent fructosyl transferase activity.

4.1. Catalytic site amino acids in the hydrolase domain of levansucrases and inulosucrases

As discussed elsewhere, the hydrolytic domain's catalytic triad consists of two invariant Ds and an E in all three groups of enzymes. *B. subtilis* levansucrase (SacB) uses D⁸⁶, D²⁴⁷ and E³⁴² as the catalytic triad and they are shown to act as the nucleophile, transition-state stabilizer and the general acid-base catalyst (proton donor), respectively. On modification of the above amino acids to Ala by SDM, the enzyme lost its activity and thus, confirming their direct involvement in catalysis [18].

In the same way, the levansucrases from *L. reuteri* uses D²⁴⁹, D⁴⁰⁴ and E⁵⁰³ as the catalytic triad in its hydrolytic domain. On modification of the above amino acids to their amide forms, viz. D²⁴⁹→N, D⁴⁰⁴→N and E⁵⁰³→Q by SDM, about 10,000-fold reduction in sucrose hydrolytic activity was observed and thus, confirming their role on hydrolysis of sucrose molecule [34].

In *B. megaterium* levansucrase, the residues Asp⁹⁵, Asp²⁵⁷ and Glu³⁵² are proposed to form the catalytic triad. After the substitution of Ala to the proposed catalytic residues by SDM (Asp⁹⁵→A, Asp²⁵⁷→A, Glu³⁵²→A), it was found that the enzyme had lost its activity [35] and thus, confirming their direct involvement in the sucrose hydrolysis. Interestingly, the variants R²⁵⁶→A and E³⁵⁰→A were also nearly inactive.

Polsinelli *et al.* [36] have determined the 3D structure of a levansucrase from *Erwinia tasmaniensis* and found the catalytic triad involved in catalysis are, Asp⁴⁶, Asp²⁰³, and Glu²⁸⁷.

Not only the levansucrases, but also the inulosucrases also use the same active site amino acids in their hydrolytic domain. Ozimek *et al.* [34] proposed that the inulosucrase of *L. reuteri* might use D²⁷², D⁴²⁴ and E⁵²³ in the catalytic site of its hydrolytic module. This was further confirmed by SDM experiments. For example, the substitution of Ala to the proposed catalytic residues (Asp²⁷²→A, Asp⁴²⁴→A, Glu⁵²³→A), led to the loss of enzyme activity.

Pijning *et al.* [37] found that the three putative catalytic residues (D²⁷², D⁴²⁵, and E⁵²⁴) in an inulosucrase from *Lactobacillus johnsonii*. These three amino acids superposed almost perfectly with those of *B. subtilis* SacB and thus, confirming both the enzymes use the same amino acids at the active sites of their hydrolytic domains. Furthermore, they found that D²⁷²→N, a nucleophilic mutant of the enzyme, exhibited only a very low residual activity and the mutant/native enzyme activity ratio was about 8×10⁻⁶.

The crystal structure of an inulosucrase from a halophilic archaeal strain, *Halalkalicoccus jeotgali*, also exhibited the same pattern of amino acids at their hydrolytic domain. The catalytic triad is found to be composed of residues D⁴⁷, D¹⁹⁷, and E²⁶⁸ [38]. Furthermore, the 3D structure of the halophilic enzyme resembled closely to other fructansucrase structures.

The crystal structure of a fructosyl transferase from the fungus, *Aspergillus japonicus*, has shown that the amino acids in the catalytic triad are, Asp⁶⁰, Asp¹⁹¹, and Glu²⁹² and these three act as nucleophile, transition-state stabilizer, and general acid/base catalyst, respectively in the fungal enzyme and further suggested that they also governed the binding of the terminal fructose at the -1 subsite for the catalytic reaction. The active site amino acids in the fungal enzyme were further confirmed by SDM analysis. It was found that the mutants D⁶⁰→A, D¹⁹¹→A, and E²⁹²→A completely lost their activity [27].

MSA analysis has also confirmed that these three completely conserved amino acids constitute the catalytic triad in the hydrolytic site of all these fructosyl transferases (Fig. 3).

4.2. Catalytic site amino acids in the transferase domain of levansucrases and inulosucrase

The catalytic site amino acids in the transferase active site are arrived at from SDM experiments, X-ray crystallographic data and MSA analysis. As already discussed elsewhere, the fructosyl transferase from *G. stearothermophilus* was found to be inactive due to replacement of a K³⁶³ to Q³⁶³ in the proposed transferase domain. The importance of this highly conserved basic amino acid in this domain was further confirmed from analysis of hundreds of fructosyl transferase sequences from levansucrases, inulosucrases and other GH68 family glycoside hydrolase enzymes from a large number of organisms (Fig. 3). It is interesting to note that it has been shown a positively charged amino acid, viz. K/R/H is crucial for the functioning of nucleotidyl transferase catalytic reactions in DNA/RNA polymerases [1-3] where it initiates the catalytic reaction by abstraction of a proton from the substrate. Furthermore, in both the types of transferases, an invariant R at -3 or -4 from the proton abstractor (Tables 1 and 2) acts in the donor selection. The involvement of a basic amino acid as the proton abstractor and an R at -3 or -4 from the proton abstractor as nucleotide/fructose donor selection amino acid are further confirmed by SDM experiments, MSA analysis, and also from X-ray crystallographic data. The third template-binding pair (L/I/V/YG) in fructosyl transferases is suggested based on the sequence similarity from a large number of nucleotidyl transferases (DNA/RNA polymerases) (Tables 1 and 2 [1-3]).

The above conclusions are further substantiated by SDM experiments on large number of fructosyl and nucleotidyl transferases. Meng and Fütterer [18] found that SDM studies on the levansucrase of *B. subtilis* SacB revealed that modifications of the residues N²⁴², K³⁶³, and Y²³⁷ (numbering of *B. subtilis* levansucrase), which are located on the surface of the catalytic cavity affect the enzyme catalytic efficiency, transfructosylation, and hydrolysis ratio by interrupting the polymerization process. Therefore, they suggested that these residues could control the chain lengths of levans. However, they concluded that the interactions mediated by these residues had not yet been identified, and the existence of additional external acceptor-binding subsites, acting as structural determinants in the elongation of levans had not yet been clarified. Furthermore, in chain A, the interactions might resemble an acceptor anchoring state, with R³⁶⁰ and K³⁶³ maintaining direct contact with fructosyl-2 of the ligand, while Y⁴¹¹ might coordinate a water-mediated contact. Therefore, it is clear that these two residues, R³⁶⁰ and K³⁶³ play an important role in the transferase active site, which is also further supported by the present MSA analysis.

Further SDM experiments have conclusively proved that these two amino acids in the transferase catalytic site play a crucial role in levan synthesis. For example, the *B. megaterium* levansucrase SacB variants, viz. Y²⁴⁷→A, Y²⁴⁷→W, N²⁵²→A, D²⁵⁷→A, and K³⁷³→A revealed novel surface motifs remote from the sucrose-binding site with distinct influence on the polysaccharide product spectrum. Consistent with the eliminated polysaccharide synthesis, the K³⁷³→A mutant showed an increased hydrolytic activity of almost 33%. Furthermore, the five structures of the SacB variants (Y²⁴⁷→A, Y²⁴⁷→W,

N²⁵²→A, D²⁵⁷→A, and K³⁷³→A) obtained at resolutions between 2.0 and 1.75 Å supported a surface-modulated transfructosylation mechanism [39]. It is interesting to note that the D²⁵⁷ is in the highly conserved -LRD²⁵⁷P- motif of Fru-binding site and the others are in its vicinity and the K³⁷³ is implicated as the proton abstractor in the transferase active site. Homann *et al.* [35] also found that the R³⁷⁰ at -3 from the proton abstractor is crucial in the levansucrase of *B. megaterium* for the transferase activity. Furthermore, they found that the residues R³⁷⁰ and N²⁵² seem to be crucial for polyfructan synthesis and are conserved in all levansucrases from Gram-positive bacteria.

Yanase *et al.* [33] found that the H²⁹⁶, the proposed proton abstractor in the transferase active site is crucial for catalysis of the transfructosylation reaction in the levansucrase of *Z. mobilis* (Table 2).

Del Rio *et al.* [26] studied the transferase active site of an inulosucrase from *L. citreum* by SDM experiments. They found that R⁶¹⁸ is an invariant amino acid in all inulosucrases and is placed at -3 from the proton abstractor K⁶²¹ and hence, suggested it could play an important role in fructose donor selection. The transfructosylation activity and product selectivity factor found in the R⁶¹⁸→K mutant was only 50% with an order of magnitude decrease, respectively.

The above SDM data and the MSA analysis confirm that the highly conserved K and the R (at -3) play important roles in the transferase reactions in levan- and inulosucrases, where they act as proton abstractor and donor selection, respectively.

5. Mechanism of Hydrolytic and Transferase Reactions in Fructosyl Transferases

5.1. Mechanism of action of the hydrolytic reaction

It is interesting to note that both the hydrolytic and transferase modules in all three groups of fructosyl transferases invariably use catalytic triads for hydrolysis and transferase reactions. Furthermore, the sucrose-binding sites and the hydrolytic and transferase reactions are virtually identical in all three groups of enzymes, confirming that they use a fully conserved structural framework for the sucrose-binding, cleavage and transferase reactions. In bacteria, the fructan synthesis is somewhat simpler as compared to plant systems, because only one enzyme with the bifunctional property (exhibiting both hydrolytic and transferase activities) is involved. By SDM and mutational analyses, Chembert and Petit-Glatron [40] found that the hydrolytic and transferase activities could be separated in levansucrases, suggesting that they are two independent activities.

The hydrolytic domain is composed of a catalytic triad: a nucleophile (Asp), a general acid/base catalyst (Glu), and a transition-state stabilizer (Asp). The hydrolytic reaction follows a double-displacement mechanism involving two steps, (i.e.) i) protonation of the glycosidic oxygen and breaking the glycosidic linkage, and ii) a nucleophilic attack on the anomeric carbon of the donor resulting in the formation of the fructosyl-enzyme intermediate. In the latter step, a water, or a sucrose molecule or a fructan serves as an acceptor resulting in the hydrolysis or transfer of the fructose to the acceptor molecule, where the acceptor is elongated by one fructosyl unit, respectively. The reaction occurs with an overall retention of the anomeric configuration of the fructosyl residue.

The amino acids in the catalytic triad involved in the hydrolysis of the sucrose molecule are; Asp⁸⁶, Glu³⁴² and Asp²⁴⁷ (they act as nucleophile, proton donor and transition state stabilizer, respectively) [18]. The nucleophilic amino acid pair, 'Trp-Asp' and the catalytic acid-base amino acid pair 'Glu-Arg', are conserved in all levansucrases. The highly conserved -E¹⁶²WSGS- and -L²⁴⁵RDPH- motifs are involved in sucrose-binding and shown in magenta.

Figure 4 A schematic diagramme showing the hydrolytic active site amino acids and its proposed mechanism of action (numberings from the *B. subtilis* levansucrase, SacB)

During the first step of the protonation reaction, the acid/base catalyst, Glu, donates a H^+ to the glycosidic bond resulting in its cleavage, followed by a nucleophilic-electrophilic attack on the anomeric carbon of the fructose unit resulting in the formation of a fructosyl-enzyme intermediate, where the C-2 of fructose forms a covalent bond with the nucleophilic Asp residue [14, 13, 18, 25]. The fructosyl-enzyme intermediate formation is supported by kinetic analysis under steady-state conditions and was also successfully isolated and studied by Chambert and Treboul [41], where they found that the β -carboxyl group of the Asp formed a covalent bond with the fructose (Fig. 4). The second Asp acts as a transition-state stabilizer in both steps, and it is based on the observation that it forms strong hydrogen bonds with the C3 and C4 hydroxyls of the fructosyl unit [34] (Fig. 4).

5.2. Mechanism of action of the fructosyl transferase reaction

A second, separate module of the same enzyme accomplishes the fructosyl transferase reaction [40]. The synthesis of fructans starts with a transfructosylation reaction in which the hydrolyzed sucrose molecules in the first step provide the fructosyl donors in which a molecule of sucrose acts as the initial acceptor of the fructosyl units. The transfer of a fructose unit to the acceptor sucrose molecule can occur via O1 to form 1-kestotriose, (the basic unit for the formation of β -(2 \rightarrow 1)-linked inulin) or via O6 to form 6-kestotriose, (the basic unit for the formation of β -(2 \rightarrow 6)-linked levan (Fig. 5). The transferase module is also composed of a catalytic triad where a basic amino acid acts as a proton abstractor, a hydrophobic/aromatic amino acid (found downstream to the catalytic proton abstractor) forms the template-binding pair and again a basic amino acid (found upstream to the catalytic proton abstractor) involves in the donor sugar selection. The proposed fructosyl transferase reaction is very similar to the well-established nucleotidyl transferase reaction [1] as discussed elsewhere. In *B. subtilis* SacB enzyme, the catalytic K abstracts a proton from the donor fructose in the first step, leading to a nucleophilic-electrophilic attack between the incoming fructose unit and the acceptor sucrose molecule and thus, establishing a glycosidic bond between the donor and the acceptor in the second step. By the same mechanism, the fructosyl units are added sequentially to the growing chain forming a levan polymer. The initial linkage on the kestotriose, either β -(2 \rightarrow 6) or β -(2 \rightarrow 1) decides the formation of a levan or an inulin polymer, essentially using the same mechanism, but accomplished by two different enzymes, viz. the levansucrases or the inulosucrases, respectively (Fig. 5). For sucrose at concentrations of >100 mM, fructosyl transferases exhibit almost an exclusive transfructosylation activity [27].

The hydrolytic domain's Fru-binding active site amino acids are in magenta and the transferase domain's active site amino acids are in green. The active site amino acids in the transferase active site domain are: Arg³⁶⁰, Lys³⁶³ and -Leu³⁷⁷GY- (for incoming fructose- selection, proton abstraction and template-binding, respectively).

Figure 5 A schematic diagramme showing the transferase active site and its proposed mechanism action (numbering from the *B. subtilis* levansucrase, SacB)

Like the nucleotidyl transferases (RNA/DNA polymerases), the fructosyl transferases are also multifunctional enzymes and possess two active site domains, one for sucrose hydrolysis (Fig. 1) and the other one for fructosyl transfer, i.e., in the first step, the sucrose molecules are hydrolyzed and in the second step a fructose unit is added to an acceptor sucrose molecule to form a trisaccharide, either 6- or 1-kestotriose (depending on the enzyme type) which is followed by sequential additions of fructose units resulting in levan or inulin polymer, respectively (Fig. 2) [37].

6. Structure and Mechanism of Action of Nucleotidyl Transferases

The nucleotidyl transferases also belong to the Main class, 'Transferases', like the fructosyl transferases, but these enzymes involve in the sequential addition of nucleoside triphosphates (NTPs) or deoxynucleoside triphosphates (dNTPs) to synthesize an RNA or a DNA molecule, respectively. DNA polymerases make sequential addition of dNTPs to the 3-OH of a primer on a template, whereas the RNA polymerases make sequential addition of NTPs on a template. Thus, both the polymerases belong to the subclass, nucleotidyl transferases. The properties and mechanisms of action of these crucial catalysts of life are already analyzed in detail and reported by this author [1-3].

DNA polymerases catalyze the polymerization of a new strand of DNA on a given template DNA, using a primer molecule. Except for viruses, there are always more than one enzyme in a living cell. For example, at least three different polymerases have been identified even in the simplest prokaryotes. There are at least five different DNA polymerases reported from *E. coli* and they are named DNA polymerases I, II, III, IV and V. The DNA polymerases, which undertake replication, are known as replicases. The *E. coli* DNA polymerase I is used as an example to explain the mechanism of action here. It was the first enzyme to be discovered and is encoded by *polA* gene. It is a single-subunit enzyme with a molecular mass of 10³ kDa (928 amino acids). The main functions of this polymerase are: i) removal of the RNA primer after genome replication and subsequent filling of the gap arising due to such removal, ii) DNA repair and iii) removal of TT dimers in UV irradiated cells. Thus, it is a multifunctional enzyme and exhibits three different activities, viz. 5'→3' DNA polymerase activity, 3'→5' exonuclease activity (proofreading function) and 5'→3' exonuclease activity (DNA repair function). There are ~ 400 copies of the enzyme per cell.

6.1. Mechanism of Nucleotidyl Transferases

6.1.1. Dynamics of DNA polymerization

DNA polymerases synthesize a new strand of DNA on a given template using a primer and the four dNTPs (Fig. 6). They add nucleotides one at a time to the 3'-OH end of the primer as shown and thus, the new strand grows from 5'→3'. The overall reaction catalyzed by DNA polymerases can be written as,

NB: PP_i, Inorganic pyrophosphate; P_i, Inorganic phosphate

The high-energy inorganic pyrophosphate is hydrolyzed immediately by the enzyme pyrophosphatase into two molecules of inorganic phosphate resulting in release of energy, which is utilized for the polymerization reaction. Such coupling of reactions drives the polymerization process only in the forward direction, i.e., the polymerized nucleotides cannot be depolymerized.

Figure 6 A schematic diagramme showing the overall reaction of DNA polymerases

As discussed elsewhere, the DNA and RNA synthesis in cells are accomplished by the nucleotidyl transferases where they use either dNTPs or NTPs, respectively. A great deal of information is available on these enzymes from a large number of sources. X-ray crystallographic structures of a large number of polymerases from both prokaryotes and eukaryotes are available. Although they exhibit significant differences in their primary structures (probably due to divergent evolution), their crystal structures are remarkably the same in overall shape. For example, in general, all DNA polymerases, irrespective of their source, have a common protein fold that resembles the shape of a half-opened "right hand" and the polymerase domain exhibits three distinct subdomains, "thumb", "palm" and "fingers" with analogous functions in all organisms [42]. The mechanism of action of *E. coli* DNA polymerase I is shown in Fig. 7 [1]

Watson-Crick base pairing of incoming dNTP to the template at the active site; Electronic transitions at the active site for proton abstraction and an electrophilic-nucleophilic attack; Proton abstraction by the active site amino acid Lys followed by an electrophilic-nucleophilic attack resulting in the formation of 3'→5' phosphodiester bond with the concomitant release of pyrophosphate; Transfer of the proton abstracted by the Lys to the pyrophosphate resulting in the formation of inorganic pyrophosphate. The high-energy bond in the inorganic pyrophosphate is hydrolyzed immediately by the enzyme pyrophosphatase (usually associated with enzyme) and the energy released is utilized by the DNA polymerase to move (translocate) to the next nucleotide, already positioned on the template. As the PPI is removed constantly from the reaction, the polymerization reaction is always unidirectional.

Figure 7 A schematic diagramme showing the steps involved in the polymerization of nucleotidyl transferases (numberings from the *E. coli* DNA polymerase I)

7. Comparative analysis of the active site amino acid domains from the two different transferases

The substrates for the two different transferases, viz. the ribose and fructose have an important similarity in structure, in that, both have a five-membered furanose ring system, suggesting the same active site amino acids could be used for polymerization reactions. This is exemplified in the following two tables. Table 1 shows the highly conserved catalytic amino acids from a large number of DNA/RNA polymerases like, single subunit (SSU) and multisubunit (MSU) DNA polymerases, RNA polymerases, RNA transcriptases from viruses to humans. Irrespective of the source and type of the polymerase, these enzymes use a catalytic triad which consists of a proton abstractor (a basic amino acid, K/R), a template-binding pair located downstream to the proton abstractor (usually an -YG- pair) and a nucleotide selection amino acid (usually a basic amino acid, R, or in some cases a Q or N is also found) at about -4 from the proton abstractor.

Table 1 Conservation of catalytic domain(s) in viral, prokaryotic and eukaryotic RNA/DNA polymerases (Proposed and Confirmed)

Polymerase Type	Polymerase Catalytic Region
1. BACTERIOPHAGES	
SSU RNA Polymerases	
SSU DNA-dep RNAPs	
T7 Viral SSU RNA pol	..620WLA ^{Y8} GVTR ^{R4} SVTK ^{R631} RSVMTLAY ^{Y9} GS-
SP6 Viral SSU RNA pol	..612WDSI ^{R9} GITR ^{R4} SLTK ^{R1} KPVMTLPY ^{R9} GS-
T3 Viral SSU RNA pol	..WLA ^{Y8} GVTR ^{R4} SVTK ^{R1} RSVMTLAY ^{Y9} GS ⁶⁴² ..
BPK11 Viral SSU RNA pol	..WLQ ^{Y8} GVTR ^{R4} KVTK ^{R1} RSVMTLAY ^{Y9} GS ⁶³⁴ ..
2. HUMAN VIRUSES	
(+) Strand RNA Viruses (SARS-Coronaviruses)	
RNA-dep RNAPs (NSP12)	
SARS-CoV-1	..STMTNR ^{R5} Q ^{R4} FHQ ^{K1} LKLSIAATR ^R GATVVIGTSKFY ^{R22} GG ⁵⁹⁷ ..
SARS-CoV-2	..STMTNR ^{R5} Q ^{R4} FHQ ^{K1} LKLSIAATR ^R GATVVIGTSKFY ^{R22} GG ⁵⁹⁷ ..
MERS-CoV	..STMTNR ^{R5} Q ^{R4} YHQ ^{K1} MLKSMATR ^R GATCVIGTTKFY ^{R22} GG ⁵⁹⁸ ..
(-) Strand, Segmented RNA Viruses	
PB1 Catalytic Subunits of the RNA-dep RNAPs	
Human influenza A virus	..477MSKK ^{K3} SYIN ^{R1} TGTFEFTSFFFYR ^{Y14} GFV-
Human influenza B virus	..666RTKR ^{N5} RSIL ^{N1} TDQRNMILEEQCY ^{Y14} AKC-
Human influenza C virus	..464IRRF ^{N4} AVCK ^{L1} IGINMSLEKSY ^{Y13} GSL
(-) Strand, Non-segmented RNA Virus	
RNA-dep RNAPs	
Human Respiratory Syncytial Virus	..291CLN ^{R4} TLNK ^{L1} SLGLRCGFNNVILTQLFLY ^{Y18} GD- (catalytic core 1) ..640QVQ ^{R5} ILAEK ^{M1} IAENILQFFPESLTRY ^{Y17} GD- (catalytic core 2)
3. PROKARYOTIC AND EUKARYOTIC MSU DNA-dependent RNAPS (mRNAs)	
a) MSU RNAP Family (Rpb2: Initiation subunits)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β subunit	..539TRE ^{R5} AGFEVR ^{R1} DVHPHY ^{Y8} GRV ⁵⁵⁸ ..
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	..851FR ^{R5} SLFFR ^{R1} SYMDQEKKY ^{Y10} GMS ⁸⁶⁹ ..
<i>S. pombe</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	..840FR ^{R5} SIFYR ^{R1} TYTDQEKKI ^{Y10} GMT ⁸⁵⁸ ..
<i>A. thaliana</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	..819FRSYR ^{R5} DEEK ^{K1} MGLVKEDF ^{Y10} GRP ⁸⁴⁰ ..
Human MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	..808FR ^{R5} SVFYR ^{R1} SYKEQESK ^{K10} GFDQ ⁸²⁵ ..
b) MSU RNAP Family (Rpb1: Elongation subunits)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β' subunit	..833NSV ^{R5} DAVKV ^{R1} SVVSC ^{R5} DTDFGVC ¹³ AHC ¹⁶ Y ^{Y17} GRDL ⁸⁶¹ ..
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAPII Rpb1 subunit	..55DPR ^{R6} LGSIDR ^{R1} NLKC ^{R5} QTC ^{R8} QEGMNEC ¹⁵ PGHF ^{Y19} GHI ⁸⁴ ..
<i>P. pastoris</i> MSU RNAPII Rpb1 subunit	..55DPK ^{R6} LGSIDR ^{R1} NFKC ^{R5} QTC ^{R8} GEGMAEC ¹⁵ PGHF ^{Y19} GHM ⁸⁴ ..
<i>A. thaliana</i> MSU RNAPII Rpb1 subunit	..54DTR ^{R7} LGTIDR ^{K1} VK ^{R4} ETC ^{R7} MANMAEC ¹⁴ PGHF ^{Y18} GYL ⁸³ ..
Human MSU RNAPII Rpb1 subunit	..59DPR ^{R6} QGVIER ^{R1} TGRC ^{R5} QTC ^{R8} AGNMTEC ¹⁵ PGHF ^{Y19} GHI ⁸⁸ ..
4. ORGANELLAR SSU RNAPS (NEPs)	
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	..TR ^{R4} KVV ^{K1} QTVMTNV ^{Y9} G ¹⁰²⁴ ..
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	..QVDR ^{R4} KLV ^{K1} QTVMTSV ^{Y9} G ⁷⁶² ..
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>Nicotiana sylvestris</i>)	..QVDR ^{R4} KLV ^{K1} QTVMTSV ^{Y9} G ⁷⁸⁸ ..
Mitochondrial RNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	..TR ^{R4} KVV ^{K1} QTVMTTV ^{Y9} G ¹⁰⁰¹ ..
Chloroplast RNA pol (<i>Oryza sativa</i> , Japonica)	..QVDR ^{R4} KLV ^{K1} QTVMTSV ^{Y9} G ⁷³⁹ ..
Chloroplast RNA pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	..QVDR ^{R4} KLV ^{K1} QTVMTSV ^{Y9} G ⁷⁷⁹ ..

1. HUMAN and ANIMAL DNA VIRUSES	
DNA-dependent RNAPs	
Smallpox RNA pol	-SR ⁴ YPD R ¹ DSMVCHRILT Y ¹² G ^{K364} -
Monkeypox virus RNA pol	-SR ⁴ YPD R ¹ DSMVCHRILT Y ¹² G ^{K364} -
Cowpox virus RNA pol	-SR ⁴ YPD R ¹ DSMVCHRILT Y ¹² G ^{K364} -
6. VIRAL DNA-dependent DNA Polymerases	
DNA pol (T7 phage)	- ⁵⁰⁹ NQIAAELPT R ⁴ DNA K ⁹² TFI Y GFL V ⁸ GAG
Human influenza A virus	- ²⁵⁶ ETLAR S ⁴ ICE K ¹ LEQSGLP V ⁹ G ^N - #gRNA
Human influenza B virus	- ²⁵⁶ ENLAK N ⁴ ICE N ¹ LEQSGLP V ⁹ G ^N - #gRNA
Human influenza C virus	- ²⁵⁸ ETVAQ K ⁴ ICE K ¹ LESGLP V ⁹ G ^N - #gRNA
Smallpox DNA pol	TEKAIYDSM Q ⁴ YTY K ⁶⁶⁰ IANSV Y ⁸ GLM-
Vaccinia DNA pol	- ⁶⁴⁸ TEKAIYDSM Q ⁴ YTY K ⁶⁶¹ IANSV Y ⁸ GLM-
Mpox DNA pol	- ⁶⁴⁸ TEKAIYDSM Q ⁴ YTY K ⁶⁶¹ IANSV Y ⁸ GLM-
7. PROKARYOTIC DNA-dependent DNA Polymerases	
DNA pol I (<i>E. coli</i>)	- ⁷⁴⁶ PLETVTSEQ R ⁴ RS A ^{K768} AIN F ⁷⁶² GLI V ⁸ GMS-
<i>Taq</i> DNA pol I (<i>T. aquaticus</i>)	- ⁶⁵⁰ PREAVDPLM R ⁴ RA A ^{K663} TINFGVL Y ⁸ GM-
<i>Pfu</i> DNA pol (<i>P. furiosus</i>)	- ⁴⁷⁸ ILLDY R ⁴ QK A ^{K489} LLANSF Y ⁸ G Y YG Y AK-
DNA pol II (<i>E. coli</i>) [@]	- ⁴⁸⁰ AKRQGNKPL S ⁴ QAL K ⁴⁹³ IIMNAF Y ⁸ GLV-
DNA pol III MSU (Replicase, <i>E. coli</i>)	- ⁶⁶¹ ISYDPVQWQ H ⁴ ESL K ⁶⁷⁴ PVLEPT Y ⁸ GII-
8. EUKARYOTIC DNA-dependent DNA Polymerases	
Yeast α DNA pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁹³¹ HKRVQCDIR Q ⁴ QAL K ⁹⁴⁴ LTANSM Y ⁸ G S CL-
Yeast α DNA pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁹⁸⁰ LKYWELDIR Q ⁴ QAL K ⁹⁹³ LTANSM Y ⁸ GCL-
Animal α DNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	- ⁹³⁷ DLILQYDIR Q ⁴ KAL K ⁹⁵⁰ LTANSM Y ⁸ GCL-
Yeast ϵ DNA pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁷⁹⁷ MIVLYDSL Q ⁴ LAH K ⁸⁰⁹ VILNSF Y ⁸ GYV-
Plant ϵ DNA pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁷⁷⁰ MVVVYDSL Q ⁴ LAH K ⁷⁸² CILNSF Y ⁸ GYV-
Animal ϵ DNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	- ⁸¹² MEVLYDSL Q ⁴ LAH K ⁸²⁴ CILNSF Y ⁸ GYV-
Yeast δ DNA pol (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)	- ⁶⁸⁸ FKRDV L NGR Q ⁴ LAL K ⁷⁰¹ IANSV Y ⁸ GFT-
Plant δ DNA pol (<i>A. thaliana</i>)	- ⁶⁷⁹ LEK A VLDGR Q ⁴ LAL K ⁶⁹² IANSV Y ⁸ GFT-
Animal δ DNA pol (<i>H. sapiens</i>)	- ⁶⁸¹ LR R QVLDGR Q ⁴ LAL K ⁶⁹⁴ VANSV Y ⁸ GFT-
9. ORGANELLAR DNA-dependent DNA Polymerases	
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> Mitochondrial DNA pol γ	- ⁷⁴¹ LGCSR R ⁴ NEA K ⁷⁴⁹ IFNYGRI Y ⁹ GAG-
<i>A. thaliana</i> Mitochondrial DNA pol γ (pol 1)	- ⁸⁷² E R ⁴ RKAK K ⁸⁷⁷ MLNFSIA Y ⁹ GK-
<i>A. thaliana</i> Mitochondrial DNA pol γ (pol 2)	- ⁸⁷⁴ E R ⁴ RKAK K ⁸⁷⁹ MLNFSIA Y ⁹ GK-
Human Mitochondrial DNA pol γ	- ⁹¹⁷ TTVGISR R ⁴ EHA K ⁹⁴⁷ IFNYGRI Y ⁹ GAG-
<i>A. thaliana</i> Chloroplast DNA pol IA	- ⁸⁷³ E R ⁴ RKAK K ⁸⁷⁸ MLNFSIA Y ⁹ GK-
<i>A. thaliana</i> Chloroplast DNA pol IB	- ⁸⁵⁷ E R ⁴ RKAK K ⁸⁶² MLNFSIA Y ⁹ GK-

Adapted from Palanivelu [1-3, 43, 44]

NEPs, Nuclear Encoded Pols; #gRNA. Genomic RNA (replicase type); Repl, Replicase. *Pfu*, *Pyrococcus furiosus*.

The confirmed active site amino acids (by SDM, X-ray crystallography and active site-directed inhibitors) are highlighted in dark blue. In *E. coli* pol I, the replacement of K⁷⁵⁸ with Ala caused a 1,000-fold reduction in k_{cat} . The Ala substitutions result in moderate to severe effects on the polymerase activity of the individual mutant enzymes. Severe loss of activity is associated with R⁷⁵⁴→A, K⁷⁵⁸→A, F⁷⁶²→A, and Y⁷⁶⁶→A (highlighted in dark blue) in the *E. coli* DNA pol I. Tyr⁷⁶⁶ and Phe⁷⁷¹ are either involved in template-primer binding or are in the vicinity of the DNA-binding track. Residues Arg⁷⁵⁴, Lys⁷⁵⁸, Phe⁷⁶², and Tyr⁷⁶⁶ appear to be required for the binding of Mg.dTTP, while only Arg⁷⁵⁴ and Lys⁷⁵⁸ are utilized in the polymerization of Mn.dTTP [45 and references therein].

In *Taq* pol I, the invariants R⁶⁵⁹ and K⁶⁶³ in the active site were found to be immutable [45 references therein].

Table 2 shows the highly conserved catalytic amino acids in the hydrolytic and transferase active site domains of fructosyl transferases, viz. levansucrases and inulosucrases. It is interesting to note, that the fructosyl transferases also follow the same transferase active site amino acid pattern like the nucleotidyl transferases and their active site is also composed of a similar catalytic triad, where a basic amino acid (K/R/H) acts as the proton abstractor, a -L/I/V/YG- could act as the template-binding pair which is placed downstream to the proton abstractor and a donor (Fru) selection amino acid usually an R which is placed at -3 from the proton abstractor. It is interesting to note that the *G. stearothermophilus* enzyme is reported to be inactive where the regular basic amino acid K is replaced by a Q.

Table 2 Proposed amino acids in the active site of hydrolytic and transferase domains of levan- and inulosucrases from different organisms.

Fru- transferase type	Invertase module's active site		Transferase module's active site		
	Nucleophile	GBM	Proton Donor	FBM	Fru selection/Proton abstractor/ Template-binding pair
1. Levansucrases					
Bacteria					
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> (P05655)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGITSNDIYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Geobacillus stearothermophilus</i> (P94468)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GS ¹ MTIDGITSNDIYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Salibacterium salarium</i> (A0A428MZE4)	-WDTW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-FRDP-	-AR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGIDDEDIYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Bacillus megaterium</i> (A0A3D8X658)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGIGQDDVYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Paenibacillus graminis</i> (A0A089MCV7)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGIGANDVYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Clostridium saccharobutylicum</i> (A0A1S8MP69)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGISDKDIYML ¹⁵ GYV-
<i>Clostridium pasteurianum</i> (R4K861)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² GSK ¹ MTIDGIGNKDVYML ¹⁵ GFT-
<i>Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus</i>	-WDTW-	-EWSG-	-QTER-	-FRDP-	-FT ³ SH ¹ R ² TTFAAGVDGPDGVY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Beijerinckia indica</i>	-WDTW-	-EWSG-	-QTER-	-FRDP-	-FT ³ SH ¹ R ² TTFAAGVDGPDGVY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Erwinia amylovora</i>	-WDTM-	-EWAG-	-QTER-	-FRDP-	-FT ³ SH ¹ K ² YTFADNLTGPDGVY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Erwinia tasmaniensis</i>	-WDTM-	-EWAG-	-QTER-	-FRDP-	-FT ³ SH ¹ K ² YTFADNLTGPDGVY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Zymomonas mobilis</i>	-WDTW-	-EWAG-	-QTER-	-FRDP-	-FT ³ SH ¹ H ² STYADGLSGPDGVY ¹⁶ GFV-
2. Inulosucrases					
a) Eubacterial Inulosucrases					
<i>Lactobacillus delibruceii</i> (E0D02545.1)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EVER-	-LRDA-	-GR ² LT ¹ R ¹ ATDIDLAKANSTIGDNVAM ¹² GFV-
<i>Streptococcus salivarius</i> (VTY24076.1)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EVER-	-LRDP-	-SR ² IS ¹ K ¹ STDAEGTVAVRGAVGDDVVML ¹² GFV-
<i>Streptococcus mutans</i> (VTY49811.1)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-ELER-	-MRDP-	-SR ² LN ¹ H ¹ G ¹ SNDDAWNKANEVVGDNVVML ¹² GYV-
<i>Convivina intestine</i> (CAH1856476.1)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-LRDS-	-TR ² LN ¹ R ¹ G ¹ SNDYAWQKANRVIGDNVAM ¹² GFV-
<i>Limosilactobacillus reuteri</i> (Q8GP32)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-MRDA-	-TR ² LN ¹ R ¹ G ¹ SNDDAWMNANYAVGDNVAM ¹² GFV-
<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i> (ACZ67286.1)	-WDSW-	-QWSG-	-EIER-	-MRDA-	-TR ² LN ¹ R ¹ G ¹ SNDDAWMAANKAVGDNVAM ¹² GFV-
b) HaloArchea Inulosucrases					
<i>Halofera gibbonsii</i>	-WDTW-	-QWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FV ³ SS ¹ H ¹ VHTFAPGLTGFDALY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Natronococcus amylolyticus</i>	-WDTW-	-QWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FL ³ SS ¹ H ¹ EHTFAEGLEGFDALY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Halalalkalicoccus jeotgali</i>	-WDTW-	-QWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FV ³ SS ¹ H ¹ DHTFAPGLEGPGLY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Halomicrobium</i> sp.	-WDTW-	-TWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FV ³ SS ¹ H ¹ DHTFAPGLDGYDALY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Haloarcula</i> sp	-WDTW-	-QWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FL ³ SS ¹ H ¹ LHTFAPGLEGFALY ¹⁶ GFV-
<i>Halorubrum saccharovororum</i>	-WDTW-	-QWAGS-	-ELER-	-FRDP-	-FV ³ CS ¹ H ¹ VHTFAPGVTGPDGLY ¹⁶ GFV-

NB: GBM, Glucose-binding motif; FBM, Fructose-binding motif.

8. Conclusion

The data presented here reveal that the enzyme active sites are designed not at random, but based on the chemical basis of a particular reaction. Therefore, it is imperative that each enzyme active site is designed based on the molecular interactions between specific amino acids at its active site and its corresponding substrate. The present data also confirm that not only the same active site amino acids are employed for the same type of reactions, but are also conserved and adapted from viruses, bacteria, plants to humans during the long evolutionary process. It is likely that the transferase domain of fructosyl transferases harbouring a similar active site amino acid structure as the nucleotidyl transferases might have been acquired from them during the evolutionary process. After tight binding of an enzyme to its substrate, the movements of the subatomic particles, viz. the proton and electron flow, could take place spontaneously between the active site and substrate molecule, effecting transformation in the substrate. A deeper understanding of the evolution of active sites of enzymes could play an important role in enzyme engineering to design novel enzymes for degrading recalcitrant substrates and also in drug development.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The author wishes to thank Dr. P. Sathiyamoorthy, Chief Scientist, GEM Research Foundation, Chennai, for the suggestions on the manuscript.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Palanivelu P. DNA Polymerases – An insight into their active sites and mechanism of action, In: Recent Advances in Biological Research, Vol 1, Chapter 2, pp 1-39, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK, ISBN: 9788193422441, DOI: 10.9734/bpi/rabr/v1; 2019
- [2] Palanivelu P. Eukaryotic Multi-subunit DNA dependent RNA Polymerases: An Insight into their Active Sites and Catalytic Mechanism. In: Advances and Trends in Biotechnology and Genetics., Vol. 1. Chapter 1, pp 1-38, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK, Print ISBN: 978-93-89246-59-9, DOI:10.9734/bpi/atbg/v1;2020.
- [3] Palanivelu P. Single Subunit RNA Polymerases: An Insight into their Active Sites and Catalytic Mechanism, In: Advances and Trends in Biotechnology and Genetics. Chapter 1, pp 1-38, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK, ISBN: 978-93-89246-59-9, DOI:10.9734/bpi/atbg/v1; 2019.
- [4] Urey, HC. On the early chemical history of the earth and the Origin of Life. Proc Natl Acad Sci (USA). 1952; 38:351.
- [5] Miller SL. A production of amino acids under possible primitive Earth conditions. Science (New Series). 1953; 117: 528-529.
- [6] Miller SL, Urey HC. (1959). "Organic compound synthesis on the primitive Earth." Science. 1959; 130: 245-251.
- [7] Criado-Reyes J, Bizzarri BM, García-Ruiz JM, Saladino R, Mauro ED. The role of borosilicate glass in Miller–Urey experiment. Sci Rep. 2021; 11:21009. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-00235-4.
- [8] Ferris JP, Hill Jr AR, Liu R, Orgel LE. Synthesis of long prebiotic oligomers on mineral surfaces. Nature. 1996; 381: 59-61
- [9] Mohajer MA, Basuri P, David G, Zindel D, Miliordos E, Signorell R. Spontaneous formation of urea from carbon dioxide and ammonia in aqueous droplets. Science. 2025; 388,1426-1430.
- [10] Service RF. Here's how the first proteins might have assembled, sparking life. Science. 2025; doi: 10.1126/science.zlr9qda.
- [11] Lahav N, White D, Chang S. Peptide Formation in the Prebiotic Era: Thermal condensation of glycine in fluctuating clay environments. Science. 1978; 201:67-69.
- [12] Choukade R, Kango N. 2021. Production, properties, and applications of fructosyltransferase: a current appraisal. Crit Rev Biotechnol. 41: 1178-1193.
- [13] Straathoff AJJ, Kieboom APG, van Bekkum H. Invertase-catalysed fructosyl transfer in water-organic solvent systems. Carbohydr Res. 1986; 146:154-159.
- [14] Hidaka H, Hirayama M, Sumi NA. Fructooligosaccharide-producing enzyme from *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 20611. Agric Biol Chem. 1988; 52:1181-1187.
- [15] Vijn I, Smeekens S. Fructan: more than a reserve carbohydrate? Plant Physiol. 1999; 120:351–360.
- [16] Srikanth R, Reddy CH, Siddartha G, Ramaiah MJ, Uppuluri KB. Review on production, characterization and applications of microbial levan. Carbohydr Polym. 2015; 120:102-114.
- [17] Maleux K, Van den Ende W. Levans in excised leaves of *Dactylis glomerata*: effects of temperature, light, sugars, and senescence. J Plant Biol. 2007; 50: 671-680.
- [18] Meng G, Fütterer K. Structural framework of fructosyl transfer in *Bacillus subtilis* levansucrase. Nat Struct Biol. 2003; 10:935-941. doi: 10.1038/nsb974

- [19] Chi ZM, Zhang T, Cao T-S, Liu X-Y, Cui W, Zhao C-H. 2011. Biotechnological potential of inulin for bioprocesses. *Bioresour Technol.* 102: 4295-4303.
- [20] Martinez-Fleites C, Ortiz-Lombardia M, Pons T., Tarbouriech N, Taylor EJ, Arrieta JG, Hernandez L, Davies G. Crystal structure of levansucrase from the Gram-negative bacterium *Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus*. *Biochem J.* 2005; 390:19-27.
- [21] Yun J. W. Fructooligosaccharides: occurrence, preparation and application. *Enz Microb Technol.* 1996; 19:107–117.
- [22] Kaur N, Gupka A. K. Applications of oligofructose in health and nutrition. *J Biosci.* 2002; 27:703-714.
- [23] Livingston DP, Hinch DK, Heyer AG. 2009. Fructan and its relationship to abiotic stress tolerance in plants. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 66: 2007-2023.
- [24] Combie J, Öner ET. From healing wounds to resorbable electronics, Levan can fill bioadhesive roles in scores of markets. *Bioinspir. Biomim.* 2018; 14. doi: 10.1088/1748-3190/aaed92.
- [25] Palanivelu, P. Fructofuranosyl hydrolases and transferases: Active sites and mechanism of action. *Indian J Microbiol.* 1998; 38: 177-185
- [26] Del Río IM, Andrade MG, Portillo FVL, Carranza CO. Exploring the role of the residues into catalytic cavity of inulosucrase from *Leuconostoc citreum* CW28. *Int J Biol Macromol.* 2024; 279: 135159.
- [27] Chuankhayan P, Hsieh CY, Huang YC, Hsieh YY, Guan HH, Hsieh YC, Tien YC, *et al.* Crystal structures of *Aspergillus japonicus* fructosyltransferase complex with donor/acceptor substrates reveal complete subsites in the active site for catalysis. *J Biol Chem.* 2010; 285: 23251-23264.
- [28] Soto M, Rivera M, Rudiño-Piñera E, Olvera C, López-Munguía A. Selected mutations in *Bacillus subtilis* levansucrase semi-conserved regions affecting its biochemical properties. *Protein Eng Des Sel.* 2008; 21:589-595.
- [29] Ozimek LK, Kralj S, van der Maarel MJEC, Dijkhuizen L. The levansucrase and inulosucrases enzymes of *Lactobacillus reuteri* 121 catalyse processive and non-processive transglycosylation reactions. *Microbiology.* 2006; 152:1187-1196.
- [30] Ozimek LK, Kralj S, Kaper T, van der Maarel MJEC, Dijkhuizen L. Single amino acid residue changes in subsite -1 of inulosucrase from *Lactobacillus reuteri* 121 strongly influence the size of products synthesized. *FEBS J.* 2006; 273:4104-4113.
- [31] Marsh PD, Bradshaw DJ. 1995. Dental plaque as a biofilm. *J Ind Microbiol Biotechnol.* 15: 169-175.
- [32] Batista FR, Hernández L, Fernández JR, Arrieta J, Menéndez C, Gómez R, Támara Y, Pons T. Substitution of Asp-309 by Asn in the Arg-Asp-Pro (RDP) motif of *Acetobacter diazotrophicus* levansucrase affects sucrose hydrolysis, but not enzyme specificity. *Biochem J.* 1999; 337:503-506.
- [33] Yanase H, Maeda M, Hagiwara E, Yagi H, Taniguchi K, Okamoto K. Identification of functionally important amino acid residues in *Zymomonas mobilis* levansucrase. *J Biochem.* 2002; 132:565-572.
- [34] Ozimek LK; van Hijum S; van Koningsvel GA, van der Maarel MJEC, van Geel-Schutten GH, Dijkhuizen L. Site-directed mutagenesis study of the three catalytic residues of the fructosyltransferases of *Lactobacillus reuteri* 121. *FEBS Letters.* 2004; 560: 131-133.
- [35] Homann A, Biedendieck R, Gotze S, Jahn D, Seibel J. Insights into polymer versus oligosaccharide synthesis: mutagenesis and mechanistic studies of a novel levansucrase from *Bacillus megaterium*. *Biochem J.* 2007; 407: 189-198.
- [36] Polsinelli I, Caliendo R, Demitri N, Benini S. The structure of sucrose-soaked levansucrase crystals from *Erwinia tasmaniensis* reveals a binding pocket for levanbiose. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2020; 21:83 <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21010083>.
- [37] Pijning T, Anwar MA, Böger M, Dobruchowska JM, Leemhuis H, Kralj S, Dijkhuizen L, Dijkstra BW. Crystal structure of inulosucrase from *Lactobacillus*: insights into the substrate specificity and product specificity of GH68 fructansucrases. *J Mol Biol.* 2011; 412:80-93.
- [38] Ghauri K, Pijning T, Munawar N, Ali H, Ghauri MA, Anwar MA Wallis R. Crystal structure of an inulosucrase from *Halalkalicoccus jeotgali* B3T, a halophilic archaeal strain. *FEBS J.* 2021; 288: 5723-5736.

- [39] Strube CP, Homann A, Gamer M, Jahn D, Seibel J, Heinz DW. Polysaccharide synthesis of the levansucrase SacB from *Bacillus megaterium* is controlled by distinct surface motifs. *J Biol Chem.* 2011; 286: 17593-17600
- [40] Chambert R, Petit-Glatron MF, Polymerase and hydrolase activities of *Bacillus subtilis* levansucrase can be separately modulated by site-directed mutagenesis. *Biochem J.* 1991; 279: 35-41.
- [41] Chambert R, Treboul GG. Levansucrase of *Bacillus subtilis* - Characterization of a stabilized Fructosyl-Enzyme complex and identification of an Aspartyl residue as the binding site of the fructosyl group. *Eur J Biochem.* 1976; 71: 493.
- [42] Steitz TA. DNA polymerases: Structural diversity and common mechanisms. *J Biol Chem.* 1999; 274:17395-17398.
- [43] Palanivelu P. An insight into the active sites of the catalytic basic protein subunit PB1 of the RNA polymerase of human influenza viruses. *World J Adv Res Rev.* 17: 625-565 (2023).
- [44] Palanivelu P. An insight into the active sites of the RNA polymerase and proofreading exonuclease of the human respiratory syncytial virus. *World J Adv Res Rev.* 2023; 18: 842-858.
- [45] Palanivelu P. An insight into the replication mechanism of smallpox and monkeypox viruses. *World J Adv Res Rev.* 2024; 23: 2239-2260.